

Master's Thesis - Industrial Mathematics

Multi-objective Integer Linear Programming approach for Automatic Software Cognitive Complexity Reduction

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MÁLAGA, JULY 2025

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Resumen

Los proyectos software son más complejos cuanto más grandes son, por lo que puede llegar a ser realmente difícil que un desarrollador que trabaje en un gran proyecto conozca y comprenda todos los detalles del mismo. Por ello, el código debe ser muy claro. Además, es altamente probable que más desarrolladores se unan a proyectos ya existentes. De ahí la importancia de que el software sea lo más sencillo posible de entender: para poder evitar errores, y sobre todo para evitar vulnerabilidades. Para conseguir este propósito, la comunidad de desarrolladores ha dedicado bastante esfuerzo en medir y mejorar la mantenibilidad del software.

Existen muchas maneras de mejorar el software sin que afecte a su funcionalidad, siendo las refactorizaciones (*refactorings*) la principal operación para este fin. Estas operaciones permiten modificar el software sin alterar su semántica, permitiendo ahorrar mucho trabajo en la corrección de errores y en la comprensión del código.

Por otra parte, para medir el esfuerzo que un desarrollador debe emplear para comprender un código se han definido muchas métricas diferentes como, por ejemplo, la complejidad cognitiva. En este trabajo se utilizará la medida de complejidad cognitiva definida por SonarSource, una empresa que desarrolla aplicaciones muy conocidas para realizar análisis estático de código. Esta medida considera las sentencias de control de flujo y su nivel de anidamiento, con el fin de expresar el esfuerzo que requiere comprender un código (por ejemplo, un método concreto).

Una de las operaciones de refactorización que permite reducir la complejidad cognitiva es la extracción de código a otros métodos. Este problema de extracción se puede modelar como un problema de optimización combinatoria. La principal dificultad es que hay distintos criterios para evaluar las soluciones obtenidas en forma de selección de secuencias de código a extraer, por lo que surge entonces la necesidad de plantear el problema de extracción de código a otros métodos como un problema de optimización multi-objetivo.

En este trabajo fin de máster se ha planteado un modelo de programación lineal entera multi-objetivo para obtener un conjunto de soluciones que reduzcan

la complejidad cognitiva de un trozo de código dado, equilibrando además otras características del código, como las líneas de código y la complejidad cognitiva del mismo. Además, se han desarrollado una serie de algoritmos para validar el modelo, y se han añadido dichos algoritmos a una herramienta que permite parametrizar la resolución del problema de reducción de complejidad cognitiva del software.

Palabras clave: complejidad cognitiva, refactorización, software, optimización, optimización multi-objetivo.

Abstract

As software projects expand, they become increasingly complex, making it challenging for a developer working on a large project to comprehend all the project details. This highlights the necessity of writing clear and concise code. Additionally, more developers will likely join existing projects. This is why it is crucial that the software is as simple as possible to understand: to avoid bugs, and above all, vulnerabilities. To achieve this purpose, the developers' community has made great efforts in measuring and improving software maintainability.

There are many ways to enhance software without changing its functionality, considering refactoring the primary process for this purpose. These operations enable the modification of the software without altering its semantics, thereby reducing the effort required for tasks such as bug fixing and code comprehension.

On the other hand, to assess the effort a developer must invest in understanding code, several metrics have been developed throughout the years, among which cognitive complexity stands out. The measure employed in this work is the one defined by SonarSource, which is a company that develops well-known applications for static code analysis. This measure takes into account the control flow statements and their respective nesting levels to express the effort that a developer must spend to understand a code (for example, a particular method).

One of the refactoring operations that allows the reduction of cognitive complexity is the extraction of code to other methods. This extraction problem can be modelled as a combinatorial optimization problem. The main difficulty arises from the existence of different criteria for evaluating the solutions obtained, so the need arises to pose the problem of code extraction as a multi-objective optimisation problem using other methods.

This master's thesis proposes a multi-objective integer linear programming model to obtain a set of solutions that reduce the cognitive complexity of a given piece of code, such as the number of lines of code and its cognitive complexity. In addition, several algorithms have been developed to validate the model. These

algorithms have been integrated into a tool that enables the parameterised resolution of the problem of reducing software cognitive complexity.

Keywords: cognitive complexity, refactoring, software, optimization, multi-objective optimization.

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1

Introduction

This chapter introduces the context relevant to the purpose of this Master’s thesis. Subsequently, the motivation is described, as well as the objectives proposed for this work and the replication package. Finally, there is a brief description of the content structure of the whole document.

1.1 Context

Current software systems are larger as they evolve, making it difficult for a developer working on a large project to know and understand all the details. It is essential to develop clear code, not only to understand it, but also because other developers will probably use or modify it. That is why there is much effort in the literature focused on ensuring code maintainability.

Cyclomatic Complexity was initially formulated as a measurement of the “testability and maintainability” of the control flow of a module. While it excels at measuring the former, its underlying mathematical model is unsatisfactory at producing a value that measures the latter. [Campbell \(2021\)](#) describes a novel Cognitive Complexity metric that remedies Cyclomatic Complexity’s shortcomings. This new measure more accurately reflects the relative difficulty of understanding, and therefore of maintaining, methods, classes, and applications. We will refer to this new metric as **CC** (from Cognitive Complexity), and it is given by a positive number that is increased every time a control flow sentence appears. Their nesting levels also contribute to the CC of the code. Although SonarSource¹ suggests keeping code’s cognitive complexity no greater than a threshold, software developers lack support to reduce the CC of their code.

¹<https://www.sonarsource.com/es/>

One way to reduce the CC associated with a method is by extracting certain pieces of code into new methods without altering any existing functionality. This strategy is called **extract method refactoring**. A **refactoring** is a transformation that preserves the original behaviour of the code. Software CC reduction involves searching for sequences of extract method refactoring operations to reduce the CC below a given threshold (Saborido et al., 2022). Recently, Saborido et al. (2024) modelled the CC reduction as an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) optimization problem, allowing the problem to be solved by exact solvers.

1.2 Motivation

To ensure clarity illustrating the difficulties developers face when reducing the CC of code, we use the `routeAPacketTo` method in the `Host` class of the `cybercaptor-server`² open-source Java project. It is shown in Figure 1.1, and it has CC = 20, which is above the maximum recommended by SonarQube³ (CC = 15).

The number of different extract method refactoring opportunities of a method with n sentences is bounded by $CR_2^n = \binom{n+2-1}{2} = \binom{n+1}{2}$, given that each extraction is delimited by its first and last sentences in the code. The running example in Figure 1.1 has 28 lines of code, so an upper bound for the number of feasible code extractions is $\binom{29}{2} = 406$. Thus, analysing all possible refactoring opportunities to find those that reduce the CC of a method under a given threshold becomes unmanageable for developers (Saborido et al., 2022). Furthermore, not all extractions are applicable, as they could break a control flow sentence (for instance, lines 11 and 12 in Figure 1.1 cannot be extracted as a new method) or they do not contribute to the CC of the method (see lines 14-16 in Figure 1.1). For the running example, we computationally checked that there are 23 applicable code extractions that reduce the initial CC of the method. However, if one needs to evaluate all the possible sequences of extract method refactoring operations, an upper bound is $2^{23} - 1 = 8,388,607$ alternatives.

Saborido et al. (2022) modelled the software CC reduction as a single-objective optimization problem, minimizing the number of code extractions to reduce the CC of Java methods to or below a given threshold. Focusing on minimising the number of extractions from a given method is a good approach, as it does not result in too many new methods distorting the initial semantics of the code. However, preliminary experiments in a software factory revealed that

²<https://github.com/fiware-cybercaptor/cybercaptor-server.git> (last accessed June 2025)

³<https://www.sonarsource.com/es/products/sonarqube/> (last accessed June 2025)

```

1 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception {
2     usedHosts.add(this);
3     if (ttl == 0) { //Problem in routing
4         throw new Exception("Routing problem...");
5     }
6     if (!hasIP(ip)) { //Packet not arrived
7         Host nextHost = null;
8         List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
9         for (Host directlyAccessibleHost: directlyAccessibleHosts) {
10            if (...) // If the packet is for a neighbour, we send it to him
11                nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
12        }
13        if (nextHost != null) {
14            nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
15        } else { //We have to look in the routing table
16            List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
17            IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
18            boolean nextHostFound = false;
19            for (Host aDirectlyAccessible: directlyAccessible) {
20                if (...) { //Search the nextHop host object
21                    aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
22                    nextHostFound = true;
23                }
24            }
25            if (!nextHostFound) { //Routing problem
26                throw new Exception("Routing problem...");
27            }
28        }
29    }
30 }

```

Figure 1.1: Method `routeAPacketTo` in the `Host` class of the open-source project `cybercaptor-server`, used as running example in the project.

just minimising the number of extractions resulted in highly unbalanced methods, both in terms of CC and lines of code (hereafter referred to as **LOC**). We surveyed 36 professional developers, and they confirmed that this type of solution was not suitable for improving code comprehension in some cases: developers preferred the code to be balanced in terms of CC and LOC. It seemed natural then to incorporate these objectives into the problem while keeping the number of extractions in mind. Solving this problem would lead to solutions that maintain both the minimum possible number of code extractions while balancing the CC and LOC of extracted methods, thus allowing for clean, readable, and maintainable code.

1.3 Objectives

The purpose of this Master's thesis is to model the software CC reduction as a multi-objective ILP (MO-ILP) optimization problem. We then propose and evaluate two main algorithms to efficiently solve this problem and reduce the CC of a method by obtaining sequences of code extractions while balancing the CC and LOC of the extracted methods. Thus, the goals of this work are the following:

- Formulating a multi-objective ILP variant of the software CC reduction problem. The three ILP objectives with which we work are to minimize the number of extractions performed to a given method and equilibrate the CC and LOC of all code extractions.
- Designing a tool, called *ILP CC reducer tool*, that integrates several multi-objective ILP problem-solving algorithms that obtain a set of solutions aimed at reducing the CC of a given method.
- Carrying out experimental validation of the proposed multi-objective ILP model and the ILP CC reducer tool using a benchmark of methods from open-source and private industrial software projects in Java.

CC reduction will be achieved by working at method level and ensuring the threshold is below 15 for each of them, as suggested by SonarQube (Saborido et al., 2022).

1.4 Development of the master's thesis

This work has been developed in the context of the SOFIA⁴ project (PLEC2023-010266): Research in an ecosystem of applications to improve productivity in the SOFTware development industry through the intensive use of Reliable AI throughout its life cycle.

The work phases in which this Master's thesis was organised are as follows:

1. Determine the concrete objectives of the problems: CC reduction.
2. Problem statement. This phase includes the mathematical modelling of the multi-objective integer linear programming problem version of the CC reduction task.
3. Implementation of the proposed model and a software tool to ease its usage.

⁴<https://www.sofiadev.eu/>

4. Experimentation using open-source projects and industry projects from Ayesa.
5. Results analysis. If necessary, steps 2 – 4 were repeated after results analysis, changing the solution statement of the unsuccessful results.

We used agile methodology to develop this master’s thesis. Although it is not possible to define a detailed weekly schedule and timing for each task in advance, we have listed all potential tasks and selected the specific ones addressed at the beginning of each sprint. After the sprint was concluded, the process was repeated for the next iteration. Throughout the development of this Master’s thesis, weekly meetings have been held to share updates and progress made on the thesis. Finally, the work phases defined above were carried out as visually depicted in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: Work phases carried out during the Master’s thesis development.

1.5 Replication package

The complete tool resulting from this Master’s thesis can be found on GitHub⁵. Similarly, the full replication package can be found on Zenodo⁶. This full replication package includes:

- All the source code developed.
- Interactive *full p-split* example’s graph.

⁵<https://github.com/anhe2p9/M2I-TFM-Adriana.git>

⁶<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15682834>

- Illustrating example's conflict graph.
- Open source projects' results.
- Results' statistics.

All the studies presented in this master's thesis can be replicated using the materials provided in this replication package.

1.6 Contents structure

The following is a brief description of the contents of each of the chapters of this document: Chapter 2 introduces the concepts and notation used in the rest of the document. Chapter 3 revises the work related to refactoring and CC, as well as the contributions of this Master's thesis. Chapter 4 presents the formulation of the proposed multi-objective ILP model. The main algorithms available for both two- and three-objective models are presented in this chapter, including the *augmented ε -constraint* algorithm, and the *hybrid method* algorithm. Chapter 5 shows the implementation of the ILP CC reducer tool at method level. It describes the functionalities of the tool's module that uses the ILP model, its architecture, and its implementation. Chapter 6 presents the experimental analysis, as well as the results obtained for two and three-objective ILP models with the different algorithms developed. Chapter 7 discusses the conclusions derived from the results obtained from the experiments, and the proposed future work, including possible extensions and improvements. Finally, Appendix A presents the user's manual for the ILP CC reducer tool, and Appendix B shows information about the solutions obtained for open-source projects that have been moved there to ease reading.

2

Concepts and notation

The concepts and notation used throughout the rest of the document are outlined in this chapter. There is a description and example of an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) of a code, useful for source code representation.

As the primary goal of this work is to reduce Cognitive Complexity (CC) of code, a description of this metric is provided in this chapter. Finally, multi-objective Integer Linear Programming is introduced.

2.1 Abstract Syntax Tree (AST)

The Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) is a data structure used in computer science to reflect the syntactic structure of a piece of code with a tree-like form. Each node in the AST represents an element that is present in the code, such as a variable declaration, a method call, a conditional, a `for` or `while` loop, among others.

The AST for the running example code in Figure 1.1 can be found in Figure 2.1. Conditionals are shown in yellow, and for loops are shown in green in the example. Both conditional sentences and `for` loops contribute to the CC of a code, so they are delineated with a red border to reflect their role in program execution. The rest of the nodes in the AST do not contribute to the CC of the code. There are four nesting levels in this example, represented with horizontal blue dashed lines, which are also numbered from 0 to 3.

Figure 2.1: AST for code in Figure 1.1.

2.2 Cognitive complexity (CC) of a code

Cognitive Complexity is a relatively novel measure of how difficult a piece of code is to understand and handle intuitively. Unlike the more traditional Cyclomatic Complexity, which focuses on the number of possible execution paths in a program, CC shifts the attention toward human factors. This new concept focuses on understandability, i.e., how long it takes a developer to understand the code. Different metrics have been defined over the years, to reduce it as much as possible. By minimizing CC, teams can improve collaboration, reduce onboarding time for new developers, and decrease the likelihood of introducing errors during future modifications.

2.2.1 Measures for code complexity

The developers' community has always sought to predict the effort required for software development or quality assessment, leading to the proposal of various metrics. In 1983, [Basili et al. \(1983\)](#) conducted an empirical study to investigate the correlation between different measures and actual data. Later in 1988, [Weyuker \(1988\)](#) presented abstract properties to compare software complexity models formally. These properties allow developers to evaluate a large number of existing software metrics. Most metrics focus on method complexity, and then the complexities of each method are added. [Weyuker \(1988\)](#) states that the complexity of a program using the data flow measure depends directly on the placement of statements and how the components interact via the potential flow of data. [Kaner and Bond \(2004\)](#) conducted an evaluation to validate proposed metrics until 2004, where they criticise the way metrics programs are used, and they try to evaluate measurements by answering 10 questions, such as their purpose, their scope, their scale, among others. [Misra et al. \(2012\)](#) proposed a suite of cognitive metrics for evaluating complexity for object-oriented codes. The progression observed over the years is that researchers sought to define a metric to measure something subjective formally. Finally, it was possible to validate a measure that can be used to determine the effort spent by a developer to understand code.

[Campbell \(2021\)](#) describes a novel Cognitive Complexity metric that takes a different approach from the use of mathematical models to evaluate code, to remedy Cyclomatic Complexity's shortcomings and produce a measurement that more accurately reflects the relative difficulty of understanding, and therefore of maintaining, methods, classes, and applications.

```

1 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception {
2     usedHosts.add(this);
3     1 if (ttl == 0) { //Problem in routing
4         throw new Exception("Routing problem...");
5     }
6     1 if (!hasIP(ip)) { //Packet not arrived
7         Host nextHost = null;
8         List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
9         1+1 for (Host directlyAccessibleHost: directlyAccessibleHosts) {
10             1+2 if (...) // If the packet is for a neighbour, we send it to him
11                 nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
12         }
13         1+1 if (nextHost != null) {
14             nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
15             1 else { //We have to look in the routing table
16                 List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
17                 IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
18                 boolean nextHostFound = false;
19                 1+2 for (Host aDirectlyAccessible: directlyAccessible) {
20                     1+3 if (...) { //Search the nextHop host object
21                         aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
22                         nextHostFound = true;
23                     }
24                 }
25                 1+2 if (!nextHostFound) { //Routing problem
26                     throw new Exception("Routing problem...");
27                 }
28             }
29         }
30     }
}

```

Figure 2.2: Example of the count of Cognitive Complexity (CC), from the example in Figure 2.7. It is shown that the inherent and nesting components are a sum of two components when a nesting component exists.

Nowadays, it is common to use static code analysers, such as SonarCloud¹ and SonarQube², to know the Cognitive Complexity (CC) of a code. CC can be computed as the sum of two components that are called the **inherent component** and the **nesting component** (Campbell, 2021):

¹<https://www.sonarsource.com/es/products/sonarcloud/> (last accessed June 2025)

²<https://www.sonarsource.com/es/products/sonarqube/> (last accessed June 2025)

- The **inherent component** contributes with +1 for each occurrence of certain control flow structures and complex expressions, such as logical operators in conditionals, loops, etc.
- The **nesting component** depends on the depth that a certain control flow structure appears in the code concerning the method declaration.

Figure 2.2 shows an example of the computation of CC of the code in Figure 1.1, where the CC of the code is 20.

2.2.2 CC reduction

Once the CC metric is defined, one would like to reduce it to a given threshold, resulting in a clean, easy-to-understand, and easy-to-manage code. The maximum cognitive complexity (CC) suggested by SonarQube for each method in a Java code is 15. CC reduction can be explained both qualitatively and quantitatively.

Qualitatively, it is easier to understand a compact code by substituting a piece of code with a line that explains its functionality, i.e., the extracted method name. Figure 2.3 shows the application of an extract method refactoring to the running example. This refactoring was manually performed using the Eclipse IDE³. The problem with this refactoring is that the name obtained with Eclipse is not very representative (`routeAPacketTo_extraction1`). This problem is addressed by Recio Abad et al. (2024). They found that the names offered by Large Language Models (LLMs) are highly acceptable. Therefore, the best option for this master's thesis is to utilize an LLM to generate a suitable name for each extraction. The name obtained for method `routeAPacketTo_extraction1` was `tryForwardToNextHop`.

On the other hand, CC reduction can be explained quantitatively. If one subtracts the metrics corresponding to the extraction of the piece of code chosen for the example, method `routeAPacketTo` CC is reduced from 22 (see Figure 2.4(a)) to 13 (see Figure 2.4(b)). The new method `tryForwardToNextHop` CC is 3 (see Figure 2.4(b)). Not only is the CC of method `routeAPacketTo` reduced, but the sum of the CC of the refactored `routeAPacketTo` and its extraction `tryForwardToNextHop` is $13 + 3 = 16$, which is lower than the initial CC (20).

³<https://eclipseide.org/>

Figure 2.3: Extract method refactoring applied to method `routeAPacketTo` of the running example.

```

1 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception {
2     usedHosts.add(this);
3     if (ttl == 0) { //Problem in routing
4         throw new Exception("Routing problem...");
5     }
6     if (!hasIP(ip)) { //Packet not arrived
7         Host nextHost = null;
8         List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
9         for (Host directlyAccessibleHost : directlyAccessibleHosts) {
10             if (...) // If the packet is for a neighbour, we send it to him
11                 nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
12         }
13         if (nextHost != null) {
14             nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
15         } else { //We have to look in the routing table
16             List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
17             IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
18             boolean nextHostFound = false;
19             for (Host aDirectlyAccessible : directlyAccessible) {
20                 if (...) { //Search the nextHop host object
21                     aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
22                     nextHostFound = true;
23                 }
24             }
25             if (!nextHostFound) { //Routing problem
26                 throw new Exception("Routing problem...");
27             }
28         }
29     }
30 }

```

(a) Original method. $CC = 20$.

```

1 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception
2     {
3         usedHosts.add(this);
4         if (ttl == 0) { //Problem in routing
5             throw new Exception("Routing problem...");
6         }
7         if (!hasIP(ip)) { //Packet not arrived
8             Host nextHost = null;
9             List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
10            for (Host directlyAccessibleHost : directlyAccessibleHosts) {
11                if (...) // If the packet is for a neighbour, we send it to him
12                    nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
13            }
14            if (nextHost != null) {
15                nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
16            } else { //We have to look in the routing table
17                List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
18                IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
19                boolean nextHostFound = false;
20                tryForwardToNextHop(ip, ttl, usedHosts, directlyAccessible, nextIP,
21                    nextHostFound);
22                if (!nextHostFound) { //Routing problem
23                    throw new Exception("Routing problem...");
24                }
25            }
26        }
27    }
28 private void tryForwardToNextHop(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts, List<Host>
29     directlyAccessible, IPAddress nextIP, boolean nextHostFound) {
30     for (Host aDirectlyAccessible : directlyAccessible) {
31         if (...) { //Search the nextHop host object
32             aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
33             nextHostFound = true;
34         }
35     }
36 }

```

(b) Refactored version. $CC = 13$ and $CC = 3$ for the `routeAPacketTo` and `tryForwardToNextHop` methods, respectively.Figure 2.4: Extract method refactoring applied to method `routeAPacketTo` of the running example in Figure 1.1, using ILP (Saborido et al., 2024).

2.2.3 Conflict graph of a method

The relationship between different feasible extractions can be conceptually represented through a conflict graph. A conflict graph is a graph where each node represents applicable extractions, and there are two types of edges: *nested* and *conflict* edges. These edges represent the relationship between each feasible extraction of the studied method, so they allow the definition of the Integer Linear Programming problem (ILP problem) defined in this Master's thesis.

The conflict graph for the running example is represented in Figure 2.5⁴, where code is added to each node to know precisely which extraction belongs to it. Each feasible extraction is represented with a different node in the conflict graph, and the number inside each node is the index $(i, j\dots)$ of each feasible extraction. Nested edges are represented with straight black arrows pointing in nesting direction, while conflict edges are represented with curved red lines. Let s_i, s_j and e_i, e_j be the start and end offsets of the i th and j th extractions, respectively.

- **Nested extractions:** we consider the j th extraction is nested in the i th extraction, denoted with $j \rightarrow i$, when $[s_j, e_j] \subset [s_i, e_i]$. In that case, we say that the j th extraction is the *descendant* of the i th extraction, and that the i th extraction is the *ancestor* of the j th extraction. Code that is nested inside another, which in turn is nested inside a third, is ultimately also nested within the third. Figure 2.5 does not display the nesting edges that would result from the transitive closure of the nesting relationship. Regarding the running example (see Figure 1.1), the first `for` loop (lines 8 – 10) is nested in the second conditional (lines 5 – 22). As we are working at method level, the code associated with the body of the original method can be defined as the 0th extraction. Thus, $i \rightarrow 0$ can be written for all $i \geq 1$, which means that all extractions are nested in the body of the original method.
- **Conflicting extractions:** we consider that the i th extraction is in conflict with the j th extraction, denoted with $i \leftrightarrow j$ when i and j are not nested one in the other, and $[s_j, e_j] \cap [s_i, e_i] \neq \emptyset$. Two extractions cannot be extracted simultaneously if they are in conflict. As depicted in Figure 2.6, the extraction of node 14, defined by lines 16 – 24, conflicts with the extraction of node 15, defined by lines 17 – 27, and then these two extractions cannot be extracted at the same time.

⁴Figure 2.5 is also available in Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15682834>.

Figure 2.5: Conflict graph of running example in Figure 1.1. Code is added to each node to identify exactly which feasible extraction it belongs to.

(a) Nodes 13, 14, and 15 of the conflict graph in Figure 2.5.

```

1 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception {
2     usedHosts.add(this);
3     if (ttl == 0) { //Problem in routing
4         throw new Exception("Routing problem...");
5     }
6     if (!hasIP(ip)) { //Packet not arrived
7         Host nextHost = null;
8         List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
9         for (Host directlyAccessibleHost: directlyAccessibleHosts) {
10            if (...) // If the packet is for a neighbour, we send it to him
11                nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
12        }
13        if (nextHost != null) {
14            nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
15        } else { //We have to look in the routing table
16            List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
17            IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
18            boolean nextHostFound = false;
19            for (Host aDirectlyAccessible: directlyAccessible) {
20                if (...) { //Search the nextHop host object
21                    aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
22                    nextHostFound = true;
23                }
24            }
25            if (!nextHostFound) { //Routing problem
26                throw new Exception("Routing problem...");
27            }
28        }
29    }
30 }

```

(b) Original method with extractions highlighted.

Figure 2.6: Example of conflicting extractions in conflict graph in Figure 2.5. Nodes are shown on the left side, and their corresponding code is highlighted in the original method from Figure 1.1 on the right side.

2.2.4 Variables used to work in CC reduction

Next, we define new variables to work in CC reduction formally. To better understand the use of each variable, Figure 2.7 shows them as comments in the running example presented in Figure 1.1, and Figure 2.1 shows the AST of the method. Each feasible extraction has a specific index, which will be represented as i and j in the notation used to define each variable. They correspond to the i th and j th extraction in the code, as shown in Figure 2.5. We show only the variables of those feasible extractions that contribute to the CC of the method. With this notation, the 0th extraction is the complete method that we want to refactor. Those variables are defined as follows:

- $\lambda_i \Rightarrow$ **nesting component** of the i th feasible extraction. Note that $\lambda_i = 0$ when no nesting exists in extraction i . $\lambda_0 = 0$ is the depth of the complete method.
 - Referring to the running example, the conditional sentence in *line 5* of Figure 2.7 has $\lambda = 0$ because its nesting level is zero, but the conditional sentence in *line 16* has $\lambda = 2$ because it is nested in the `for` loop in *line 14*, and that `for` loop is in turn nested in the conditional sentence in *line 10*.
- $\iota_i \Rightarrow$ **accumulated inherent component** of the i th extraction and the ones contained by it.
 - Referring to the running example, the conditional sentence in *line 37* found in Figure 2.8 has $\iota = 1$ because the unique contribution to the inherent component inside that sentence is itself. But the conditional sentence in *line 21* has $\iota = 5$ because inside that sentence there are the `else` sentence of *line 24* (with $\iota = 4$), the `for` loop in *line 29* (with $\iota = 2$), the conditional sentence in *line 31* (with $\iota = 1$), and the conditional sentence in *line 37* (with $\iota = 1$).
- $\nu_i \Rightarrow$ **accumulated nesting component** of the extractions contained by the i th extraction (considering nesting 0 for the i th extraction) (see Figures 2.9 and 2.10). The total accumulated nesting component of the complete method, ν_0 , is obtained by adding every contribution ν_i to the zero extraction (that is, the complete method).
 - Referring to the running example, the `for` loop in *line 29* found in Figure 2.9 contributes to the accumulated nesting component of the method with $+2$ because

its nesting level is $\lambda = 2$. On the other hand, the conditional sentence in *line 31* contributes to the accumulated nesting component of the method in the running example with $+3$ because its nesting level is $\lambda = 3$. Both sentences contribute to the accumulated nesting component of the method with $\nu_i = +2 + 3 = +5$.

- The accumulated nesting component can be calculated in the same way using the AST of the code, which is shown in Figure 2.10.
- $\mu_i \Rightarrow$ **number of extractions that contribute to the accumulated nesting component** of the i th feasible extraction (including itself when its nesting component is not 0) (see Figure 2.11).
 - Referring to the running example, the `for` loop in *line 29* found in Figure 2.11 has $\mu = 2$ because both the conditional sentence inside it (*line 31*) and the `for` loop itself contribute to the nesting level. Hence, they are two sentences contributing, then $\mu = 2$.
 - In the case of the `else` sentence in *line 24* in Figure 2.11, $\mu = 3$ because it has three sentences that contribute to the nesting level. They are the `for` loop in *line 29*, the conditional sentence in *line 31*, and the conditional sentence in *line 37*. Note that the `else` sentence does not contribute to the nesting level (Campbell, 2021), even though this sentence nesting level is different from 0. That is why there is no contribution to μ in this `else` sentence, as it can be observed in Figure 2.11.
 - In the case of the conditional sentence in *line 5*, its μ value is 0 because it does not contribute to the nesting level and it does not have any feasible extractions that contribute to the nesting level inside it.

Once every variable is obtained as explained above, they can be combined to define the following:

- $CCR_{j \rightarrow i} = \iota_j + \nu_j + |\lambda_j - \lambda_i| \mu_j \Rightarrow$ **CC reduction** when extracting j from i .
- $NMCC_i = \iota_i + \nu_i \Rightarrow$ **CC of the new method** when extracting i .

```

1 // Cognitive complexity 20
2 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception {
3     usedHosts.add(this);
4     // [ $\lambda=0, \iota=1, \nu=0, \mu=0, \text{CCR}=1, \text{NMCC}=1$ ]
5     if (ttl == 0) { // Problem in routing
6         throw new Exception("Routing problem, TTL is null : packet to "
7             + ip + " deleted on host " + this.getName());
8     }
9     // [ $\lambda=0, \iota=8, \nu=11, \mu=6, \text{CCR}=19, \text{NMCC}=19$ ]
10    if (!hasIP(ip)) { // Packet not arrived
11        Host nextHost = null;
12        List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
13        // [ $\lambda=1, \iota=2, \nu=1, \mu=2, \text{CCR}=5, \text{NMCC}=3$ ]
14        for (Host directlyAccessibleHost: directlyAccessibleHosts) {
15            // [ $\lambda=2, \iota=1, \nu=0, \mu=1, \text{CCR}=3, \text{NMCC}=1$ ]
16            if (directlyAccessibleHost.hasIP(ip)) // If the packet is for a neighbour,
17                // We send it to him
18                nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
19        }
20        // [ $\lambda=1, \iota=5, \nu=4, \mu=4, \text{CCR}=13, \text{NMCC}=9$ ]
21        if (nextHost != null) {
22            nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
23            // [ $\lambda=1, \iota=4, \nu=4, \mu=4, \text{CCR}=13, \text{NMCC}=9$ ]
24        } else { // We have to look in the routing table
25            List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
26            IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
27            boolean nextHostFound = false;
28            // [ $\lambda=2, \iota=2, \nu=1, \mu=2, \text{CCR}=7, \text{NMCC}=3$ ]
29            for (Host aDirectlyAccessible: directlyAccessible) {
30                // [ $\lambda=3, \iota=1, \nu=0, \mu=1, \text{CCR}=4, \text{NMCC}=1$ ]
31                if (aDirectlyAccessible.hasIP(nextIP)) { // Search the nextHop host object
32                    aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
33                    nextHostFound = true;
34                }
35            }
36            // [ $\lambda=2, \iota=1, \nu=0, \mu=1, \text{CCR}=3, \text{NMCC}=1$ ]
37            if (!nextHostFound) { // Routing problem
38                throw new Exception("Routing problem, there is no route corresponding
39                    to the packet or the destination host is on the internet");
40            }
41        }
42    }
43 }

```

Figure 2.7: Method `routeAPacketTo` in the `Host` class of the open-source project `cybercaptor-server`, used as running example in the project. Comments show CC metrics of those statements contributing to the cognitive complexity of the method.

```

1 // Cognitive complexity 20
2 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception {
3     usedHosts.add(this);
4     // [ $\lambda=0$ ,  $\ell=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=0$ , CCR=1, NMCC=1]
5     if (ttl == 0) { // Problem in routing
6         1 throw new Exception("Routing problem, TTL is null : packet to "
7             + ip + " deleted on host " + this.getName());
8     }
9     // [ $\lambda=0$ ,  $\ell=8$ ,  $\nu=11$ ,  $\mu=6$ , CCR=19, NMCC=19]
10    if (!hasIP(ip)) { // Packet not arrived
11        Host nextHost = null;
12        List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
13        8 // [ $\lambda=1$ ,  $\ell=2$ ,  $\nu=1$ ,  $\mu=2$ , CCR=5, NMCC=3]
14        for (Host directlyAccessibleHost: directlyAccessibleHosts) {
15            // [ $\lambda=2$ ,  $\ell=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=1$ , CCR=3, NMCC=1]
16            2 if (directlyAccessibleHost.hasIP(ip)) // If the packet is for a neighbour,
17                // We send it to him
18                1 nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
19        }
20        // [ $\lambda=1$ ,  $\ell=5$ ,  $\nu=4$ ,  $\mu=4$ , CCR=13, NMCC=9]
21        if (nextHost != null) {
22            5 nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
23            // [ $\lambda=1$ ,  $\ell=4$ ,  $\nu=4$ ,  $\mu=3$ , CCR=12, NMCC=9]
24        } else { // We have to look in the routing table
25            List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
26            IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
27            boolean nextHostFound = false;
28            // [ $\lambda=2$ ,  $\ell=2$ ,  $\nu=1$ ,  $\mu=2$ , CCR=7, NMCC=3]
29            4 for (Host aDirectlyAccessible: directlyAccessible) {
30                // [ $\lambda=3$ ,  $\ell=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=1$ , CCR=4, NMCC=1]
31                2 if (aDirectlyAccessible.hasIP(nextIP)) { // Search the nextHop host object
32                    1 aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
33                    nextHostFound = true;
34                }
35            }
36            // [ $\lambda=2$ ,  $\ell=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=1$ , CCR=3, NMCC=1]
37            if (!nextHostFound) { // Routing problem
38                1 throw new Exception("Routing problem, there is no route corresponding
39                    to the packet or the destination host is on the internet");
40            }
41        }
42    }
43 }

```

Figure 2.8: Count of accumulated inherent component, ℓ , from the example in Figure 2.7.

```

1 // Cognitive complexity 20
2 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception {
3     usedHosts.add(this);
4     // [ $\lambda=0$ ,  $\iota=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=0$ , CCR=1, NMCC=1]
5     if (ttl == 0) { // Problem in routing
6         throw new Exception("Routing problem, TTL is null : packet to "
7             + ip + " deleted on host " + this.getName());
8     }
9     // [ $\lambda=0$ ,  $\iota=8$ ,  $\nu=1$ ,  $\mu=6$ , CCR=19, NMCC=19]
10    if (!hasIP(ip)) { // Packet not arrived
11        Host nextHost = null;
12        List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
13        // [ $\lambda=1$ ,  $\iota=2$ ,  $\nu=1$ ,  $\mu=2$ , CCR=5, NMCC=3]
14        ← +1 for (Host directlyAccessibleHost: directlyAccessibleHosts) {
15            ← +1 // [ $\lambda=2$ ,  $\iota=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=1$ , CCR=3, NMCC=1]
16            ← +1 if (directlyAccessibleHost.hasIP(ip)) // If the packet is for a neighbour,
17                // We send it to him
18                nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
19        }
20        // [ $\lambda=1$ ,  $\iota=5$ ,  $\nu=4$ ,  $\mu=4$ , CCR=13, NMCC=9]
21        ← +1 if (nextHost != null) {
22            nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
23        }
24        // [ $\lambda=1$ ,  $\iota=4$ ,  $\nu=4$ ,  $\mu=3$ , CCR=12, NMCC=9]
25        ← +0 else { // We have to look in the routing table
26            List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
27            IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
28            boolean nextHostFound = false;
29            // [ $\lambda=2$ ,  $\iota=2$ ,  $\nu=1$ ,  $\mu=2$ , CCR=7, NMCC=3]
30            ← +1 for (Host aDirectlyAccessible directlyAccessible) {
31                ← +1 // [ $\lambda=3$ ,  $\iota=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=1$ , CCR=4, NMCC=1]
32                ← +1 if (aDirectlyAccessible.hasIP(nextIP)) { // Search the nextHop host object
33                    aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
34                    nextHostFound = true;
35                }
36            }
37            // [ $\lambda=2$ ,  $\iota=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=1$ , CCR=3, NMCC=1]
38            ← +1 if (!nextHostFound) { // Routing problem
39                throw new Exception("Routing problem, there is no route corresponding
40                    to the packet or the destination host is on the internet");
41            }
42        }
43    }

```

Figure 2.9: Count of accumulated nested component, ν , from the example in Figure 2.7. Note that the else sentence does not increment the nested component, just the inherent one.

Figure 2.10: Count of accumulated nesting component, ν , from the AST in Figure 2.1.

```

1 // Cognitive complexity 20
2 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception {
3     usedHosts.add(this);
4     // [ $\lambda=0$ ,  $\iota=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=0$ ], CCR=1, NMCC=1]
5     if (ttl == 0) { // Problem in routing
6         throw new Exception("Routing problem, TTL is null : packet to "
7             + ip + " deleted on host " + this.getName());
8     }
9     // [ $\lambda=0$ ,  $\iota=8$ ,  $\nu=11$ ,  $\mu=6$ ], CCR=19, NMCC=19]
10    if (!hasIP(ip)) { // Packet not arrived
11        Host nextHost = null;
12        List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
13        // [ $\lambda=1$ ,  $\iota=2$ ,  $\nu=1$ ,  $\mu=2$ ], CCR=5, NMCC=3]
14        for (Host directlyAccessibleHost: directlyAccessibleHosts) {
15            // [ $\lambda=2$ ,  $\iota=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=1$ ], CCR=3, NMCC=1]
16            1 if (directlyAccessibleHost.hasIP(ip)) // If the packet is for a neighbour,
17                // We send it to him
18                1 nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
19        }
20        // [ $\lambda=1$ ,  $\iota=5$ ,  $\nu=4$ ,  $\mu=4$ ], CCR=13, NMCC=9]
21        if (nextHost != null) {
22            1 nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
23            // [ $\lambda=1$ ,  $\iota=4$ ,  $\nu=4$ ,  $\mu=3$ ], CCR=12, NMCC=9]
24        } else { // We have to look in the routing table
25            List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
26            IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
27            boolean nextHostFound = false;
28            // [ $\lambda=2$ ,  $\iota=2$ ,  $\nu=1$ ,  $\mu=2$ ], CCR=7, NMCC=3]
29            for (Host aDirectlyAccessible: directlyAccessible) {
30                // [ $\lambda=3$ ,  $\iota=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=1$ ], CCR=4, NMCC=1]
31                1 if (aDirectlyAccessible.hasIP(nextIP)) { // Search the nextHop host object
32                    1 aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
33                    nextHostFound = true;
34                }
35            }
36            // [ $\lambda=2$ ,  $\iota=1$ ,  $\nu=0$ ,  $\mu=1$ ], CCR=3, NMCC=1]
37            if (!nextHostFound) { // Routing problem
38                1 throw new Exception("Routing problem, there is no route corresponding
39                    to the packet or the destination host is on the internet");
40            }
41        }
42    }
43 }

```

Figure 2.11: Count of the contribution of accumulated nesting component, μ , from the example in Figure 2.7.

2.3 Linear programming

Linear Programming aims to optimize a linear function subject to a set of inequalities (Cormen et al., 2009). Given a set of real numbers a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n and a set of variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , we define a **linear function** f on those variables by

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_nx_n = \sum_{j=1}^n a_jx_j. \quad (2.1)$$

If b is a real number and f is a linear function, then the equation $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = b$ is a **linear equality** and the inequalities $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \leq b$ and $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \geq b$ are **linear inequalities**. We use the general term **linear constraints** to denote either linear equalities or inequalities. In linear programming, we do not allow strict inequalities. Formally, a **linear-programming problem** is the problem of either minimizing or maximizing a linear function subject to a finite set of linear constraints. If we are to minimize, then we call the linear program a **minimization linear program**. If we are to maximize, then we call the linear program a **maximization linear program**.

2.3.1 Integer linear programming

An **integer linear-programming problem** (ILP) is a linear-programming problem with the additional constraint that the variables x must take on integral values. Determining whether an integer linear program has a feasible solution is NP-hard, which means there is no known polynomial-time algorithm to solve this problem.

2.3.2 Mixed integer linear programming

A **mixed integer linear-programming problem** (MILP) is a linear-programming problem with both integer and continuous variables.

2.4 Multi-objective optimization

It is common to find problems in the real world where we need to optimize multiple objectives simultaneously. In these cases, the objectives often conflict, as optimizing one typically results in the rest deteriorating. The goal then is to find a set of solutions that satisfy every constraint,

where no objective can be improved without worsening at least one of the others. A multi-objective optimization problem can be formulated as follows (Saborido et al., 2025):

$$\text{minimize} \quad \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = (f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_k(\mathbf{x}))^T \quad (2.2)$$

$$\text{s.t} \quad \mathbf{x} \in S, \quad (2.3)$$

where:

- $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)^T \in S$ is the vector of **decision variables**.
- $S \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is the **decision space** of feasible solutions.
- $f_i : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $i = 1, \dots, k$, with $k \geq 2$ are the **objective functions** to be optimized.
- The image of S in \mathbb{R}^k , i.e. $Z = \mathbf{f}(S) \subset \mathbb{R}^k$, is the **objective space**.
 - The objective space is composed of the objective vectors as $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$, for any $\mathbf{x} \in S$.

2.4.1 Pareto front

Since the objectives are often conflicting, finding a single decision vector (solution) that optimizes all the objectives simultaneously is usually impossible. Thus, much attention is given to the so-called Pareto optimal solutions for which none of the objectives can be improved without deteriorating at least one of the others. The set of Pareto optimal points (usually called “solutions” due to an abuse of language) in the decision space is called the Pareto optimal set, and its image in the objective space is the Pareto front (PF) (Saborido et al., 2025).

For $\mathbf{z}, \bar{\mathbf{z}} \in \mathbb{R}^k$, we can find the following scenarios, as shown in Figure 2.12, which is an example of a PF in the objective space:

- **Dominated solutions** (see the brown solution in Figure 2.12): \mathbf{z} *dominates* $\bar{\mathbf{z}}$ if and only if $z_i \leq \bar{z}_i$ for all $i = 1, \dots, k$, and $z_j < \bar{z}_j$ for, at least, one index j .
- **Efficient solutions** (see the blue solutions in Figure 2.12): one solution is efficient if there is no other solution in the search space that dominates it.
- **Unsupported efficient solutions** (see the green solution in Figure 2.12): \mathbf{z} is an unsupported efficient solution if it cannot be obtained by minimizing a linear combination

of the objectives. Therefore, unsupported solutions, although they are non-dominated solutions, are not found in the convex envelope of the PF.

- **Weakly dominated solutions** (see the red solutions in Figure 2.12): \mathbf{z} *weakly dominates* $\bar{\mathbf{z}}$ if we can just assure that $z_i \leq \bar{z}_i$ for all $i = 1, \dots, k$.

Figure 2.12: Objective space example and types of solutions that may appear in the objective space. Dominated solutions do not belong to the PF.

A **non-dominated solution set** is a set of solutions whose objective vectors are not dominated among them. For two non-dominated solution sets A and B (in the objective space \mathbb{R}^k), we say that A *strictly dominates* B (or that A is *better* than B) if, for every $\mathbf{z} \in B$, there is at least one $\mathbf{y} \in A$ such that \mathbf{y} weakly dominates \mathbf{z} (and this means that A *weakly dominates* B), but there exists at least one solution in A that is not weakly dominated by any solution in B (i.e. B does not weakly dominate A).

3

Related work

This chapter introduces related work on software refactoring, cognitive complexity, and the various measures that have been proposed over the years to maintain code simplicity. It is important to note that refactorings are used as resources to modify code, maintaining its semantics, to enhance its readability, or the interoperability between different tools. In the case of improving readability, the use of refactorings is a good opportunity to reduce struggles for code maintainability.

A significant portion of the time spent on software project development is dedicated to writing code that performs specific tasks and fulfils initial requirements. Then, some time is needed to modify that code and make it more efficient, less complex, more legible, and more maintainable. This modification is known as **refactoring**, and it might require a significant amount of time. Existing literature hints at the existence of poor reviewing practices, i.e., *anti-patterns*, that may contribute to a slowdown in integration and may affect the overall sustainability of the project (Chouchen et al., 2021) and should be avoided. If design patterns are solutions to common problems encountered in software development, anti-patterns are solutions that apparently solve the problem, but the resulting code is hardly maintainable and reusable. To avoid the use of anti-patterns, developers apply changes to code that enhance the design without altering its functionality, with the so-called refactorings. When one refactors code, the developer has the chance to improve the legibility without changing the code semantics. By definition, refactoring operations preserve the code semantics. The refactoring research effort is fragmented over several research communities, various domains, and objectives (Abid et al., 2020). Opdyke and Johnson (1990) first used the term *Refactoring* in September 1990. Two years later, they defined a set of refactorings, which they described as

“program restructuring operations”, that they said to support the design, evolution, and reuse of object-oriented application frameworks (Opdyke, 1992). The first book about refactoring was published by Fowler et al. (1999), and the use of refactoring became more popular, defining the refactoring process as “small changes and testing after each change”. Later, Stroggylos and Spinellis (2007) analysed different source codes to evaluate software enhancement due to refactoring, because they noticed that measurements on real life did not indicate an increase on quality achieved via code refactoring. Kaur, Amandeep and Kaur, Manpreet (2016) also carried out an analysis about code refactoring impact on Software Quality, where they define it as “a way to clean up code that minimizes the chances of introducing bugs”. They concluded that refactoring reduces software complexity, making it easily understandable. Developers’ productivity is improving due to the long-term effect of refactoring, specifically increasing two crucial factors: **understandability** and **maintainability** of the code. Extract method refactoring can help avoid cloned code, a code smell that can lead to bugs. If there are code clones, a solution to this code smell is to put that piece of repeated code inside a new method, and to replace each appearance of that code clone with a call to that new method. Several tools repair this code smell automatically. Extract method refactoring can also be used to reduce the CC of a code, as it “postpones” the effort of understanding a particular piece of code. Thus, the developer can focus on the functionality of the code and check the new method if more details are needed.

The problem of reducing CC has been approached in recent years in different ways. Saborido et al. (2022) analysed the difficulties faced by developers when deciding the best method to extract to reduce the CC of Java code and proposed enumerative approaches for CC reduction. Recently, Saborido et al. (2024) modelled the software CC reduction task as an ILP optimization problem. The purpose was to minimize the number of sentences extracted from a method, so that there is not a high quantity of extractions obtained. For each method with CC greater than a given threshold, their approach searches for sequences of applicable extract method refactoring operations. Finally, it outputs the changes to perform on each method. They were able to reduce the CC to or below the default threshold in the majority of the methods under study, enhancing the performance of the search in comparison to the results found by Saborido et al. (2022), where they used enumerative approaches.

We model the source code CC reduction as a multi-objective ILP optimization problem. **Multi-objective optimization problems** aim to simultaneously optimize multiple conflict-

ing objectives, which commonly arise in real-world scenarios. In recent years, numerous metaheuristic algorithms have been developed to tackle these problems. These approaches seek to approximate the PF, which consists of all Pareto optimal solutions, by generating a set of non-dominated solutions. Despite the previous, there exist exact algorithms to find the PF. [Chicano et al. \(2016\)](#) proposed two strategies based on ILP that can find the complete PF, and the solutions obtained are well distributed at any time of the execution, i.e., *anytime* algorithms. They developed an augmented ε -constraint algorithm (*AUGMECON*), that solves one sub-problem on each iteration, and guarantees that the non-dominated point obtained is efficient. They also improved existing anytime algorithms. As a result of his PhD, [Miguel Ángel Domínguez Ríos \(2022\)](#) proposed novel algorithms that compute the complete PF for combinatorial problems or problems with integer variables, dividing the objective space into several subspaces via specific constraints. [Ángel Domínguez-Ríos et al. \(2021\)](#) designed an exact algorithm which solves any multi-objective combinatorial optimisation (MOCO) problem, and whose solutions obtained are well distributed over the objective space anytime. They also designed an anytime hybrid algorithm, called *MOFeLS*, that uses an ILP solver and local search to solve any multi-objective problem with binary variables and linear objective functions and constraints ([Domínguez-Ríos et al., 2021](#)). Moreover, they implemented an anytime approximated algorithm, called *HBOXES*, that can become an exact algorithm depending on the input parameters, and that solves any MOCO problem ([Miguel Ángel Domínguez Ríos, 2022](#)).

3.1 Contributions

The unique techniques that can automatically reduce methods' CC to a given threshold were proposed by [Saborido et al. \(2022\)](#) and by [Saborido et al. \(2024\)](#). They reduce the CC of methods by minimizing the number of code extractions. However, they do not take into account the balance of CC among the resulting methods or the length (LOC) of code extractions. That is why the approach presented in this Master's thesis is novel, as it balances CC and LOC, thereby allowing developers more operational leeway to further edit the code after applying the tool presented in this master's thesis. While in related work the focus was solely on reducing cognitive complexity by minimizing the number of extracted methods, our proposal introduces a multi-objective perspective that integrates the balance of CC and LOC among the resulting methods, i.e., the original method and all its extractions performed. This contri-

bution is particularly relevant in collaborative and long-term projects, where readability and maintainability of code are highly relevant. If no single method remains with high CC and none of them is particularly longer than the others, then the refactored code becomes more uniform and manageable. This approach facilitates future modifications and extensions. Furthermore, this balance provides developers with the flexibility to continue editing the code without compromising quality or easily exceeding CC thresholds again.

To the best of our knowledge, no existing works or tools available in the industry address this balance explicitly using a multi-objective ILP formulation, which positions this contribution as a significant advancement in the field of automated refactoring.

4

ILP models and resolution algorithms

The formulation of the multi-objective ILP model starts from the model developed by [Saborido et al. \(2024\)](#), adding new objectives and constraints to enhance its operation on a code. The reduction of CC to a given threshold is then formulated as a multi-objective optimization problem. New objectives added to the initial problem allow the developer to refactor the code by reducing the CC while balancing the LOC and the CC of the extracted methods. As described in [Section 2.4](#), it is usually impossible to find a single solution optimizing all the objectives at the same time, and much attention is given to the so-called Pareto optimal solutions, for which none of the objectives can be improved without deteriorating, at least, one of the others.

To build the multi-objective ILP model for a given code, it is necessary to define each feasible extraction by associating each variable with its index in the conflict graph (see [Subsection 2.2.3](#)). All information related to each feasible extraction and the conflict graph of each method will serve as input to the approach developed in this Master's thesis. Once the multi-objective ILP model is defined, three algorithms are developed to solve this new model, and one of them is applied to test it. They are also described in this chapter.

4.1 Initial single-objective ILP model

It is useful to simplify the notation with the coefficients $NMCC_i$ and $CCR_{j \rightarrow i}$ defined in Section 2.2.4 (repeated here)

$$NMCC_i = \nu_i + \nu_i \quad (4.1)$$

$$CCR_{j \rightarrow i} = \nu_j + \nu_j + |\lambda_j - \lambda_i| \mu_j \quad (4.2)$$

where Eq. (4.1) is the definition of the CC of the extraction i when extracted as a new method, and Eq. (4.2) is the definition of the CC reduction, i.e., the CC that would be subtracted from extraction i in case extraction j is selected. Note that if one extraction is not nested, then $NMCC_j = CCR_{j \rightarrow i}$, since λ_j would be 0 in that case. That is why one would like to extract a sequence of lines of code that is deeply nested but also has a high $NMCC$, because in that case, both the original method and the extracted method would experience a large CC reduction. These two coefficients were added concerning the notation used by Saborido et al. (2024).

The original model proposed by Saborido et al. (2024) minimizes the number of extractions from a method while ensuring that all extractions in the code, as well as the original method, have CC lower than (or equal to) 15 after the application of the approach. They describe a zero-one program (an integer program in which the variables can only take values 0 or 1) to model the reduction of the CC of a method to a given threshold τ as

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (4.3)$$

subject to:

$$x_i + x_j \leq 1 \quad \forall i \leftrightarrow j \quad (4.4)$$

$$\underbrace{NMCC_i}_{\text{Term A}} x_i - \underbrace{\sum_{j:j \rightarrow i} CCR_{j \rightarrow i} z_{ji}}_{\text{Term B}} \leq \tau \quad \forall i = 0, 1, \dots, n \quad (4.5)$$

$$z_{ji} + |\{l | j \rightarrow l \rightarrow i\}| (z_{ji} - 1) \leq x_j - \sum_{l:j \rightarrow l \rightarrow i} x_l \quad \forall j \rightarrow i \quad (4.6)$$

$$x_0 = 1 \quad (4.7)$$

$$x_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (4.8)$$

$$z_{ji} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall j \rightarrow i \quad (4.9)$$

where n is the number of feasible extractions and x_i is a binary variable that takes the value 1 if the i -th extraction is extracted, and 0 otherwise. The goal, expressed in Eq. (4.3), is to minimize the number of extractions performed. Eq. (4.4) ensures that at most one of two feasible extractions in conflict will be selected in the final solution. It avoids choosing two feasible extractions that are in conflict simultaneously. Eq. (4.5) limits the CC of all the extractions in the code after applying the refactoring operations to be lower or equal to τ . On the left-hand side, we find the CC of the i th extraction when extracted as a new function/method (Term A) minus the CC removed from extraction i due to code extractions j contained in i (Term B). If there were two feasible extractions k and j with $k \rightarrow j \rightarrow i$ that are extracted, one should only subtract the j th extraction CC contribution, and not k . The reason is that the contribution of extraction k is already considered in the contribution of j . For this reason, x variables are not used in the expression of the CC reduction (Term B). Instead, new variables z_{ji} are defined for $j \rightarrow i$ that are one if and only if the j th feasible extraction is selected and no other extraction strictly between j and i is selected. If $z_{ji} = 1$, then one should subtract from the CC of the i th extraction the CC of the j th extraction. This is what Eq. (4.5) does. Variables z are completely determined by the values of the x variables. Eq. (4.6) expresses the relationship between the z variables and the x variables. If $z_{ji} = 1$, then $x_j = 1$ and $x_l = 0$ for all l with $j \rightarrow l \rightarrow i$. If $z_{ij} = 0$, then there is no constraint for the x variables. Eq. (4.7) forces the CC reduction of the original function/method (represented with the 0th extraction). Finally, Eqs. (4.8) and (4.9) define the binary domain of the variables.

4.2 Multi-objective ILP model

Recalling the definitions in Subsection 2.4, the vector of decision variables is the vector formed by every feasible extraction (i.e., each node in the conflict graph). As the feasible extractions can be selected or not selected, the ILP problem will be binary (as it was in the single-objective ILP problem). However, the goal will be to minimize the following objective functions:

1. Number of extractions: $\sum_{i=1}^n x_i$.

2. Differences between the highest and the lowest CC of all the extracted methods: $c_M - c_m$.
Where c_M and c_m are the maximum and minimum CC reached by all the extracted methods, respectively.

3. Differences between the highest and the lowest LOC of all the extracted methods: $t_M - t_m$.

Where t_M and t_m are the maximum and minimum LOC reached by all the extracted methods, respectively.

We balance both the amount of LOC and the CC of each extraction after the extract method refactoring is performed. For that purpose, two new objectives were added to the base model to ensure that the differences between the maximum and minimum of LOC and CC are minimal too.

Finally, the multi-objective ILP problem can be modelled as

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (4.10)$$

$$\min c_M - c_m \quad (4.11)$$

$$\min t_M - t_m \quad (4.12)$$

subject to:

$$x_i + x_j \leq 1 \quad \forall i \leftrightarrow j \quad (4.13)$$

$$NMCC_i \cdot x_i - \sum_{j,j \rightarrow i} CCR_{j \rightarrow i} \cdot z_{ji} \leq \tau \quad \forall i = 0, 1, \dots, n \quad (4.14)$$

$$z_{ji} + |\{l | j \rightarrow l \rightarrow i\}| (z_{ji} - 1) \leq x_j - \sum_{l,j \rightarrow l \rightarrow i} x_l \quad \forall j \rightarrow i \quad (4.15)$$

$$c_M \geq NMCC_i \cdot x_i - \sum_{j,j \rightarrow i} CCR_{j \rightarrow i} \cdot z_{ji} \quad \forall i = 0, 1, \dots, n \quad (4.16)$$

$$c_m \leq \tau(1 - x_i) + NMCC_i \cdot x_i - \sum_{j,j \rightarrow i} CCR_{j \rightarrow i} \cdot z_{ji} \quad \forall i = 0, 1, \dots, n \quad (4.17)$$

$$t_M \geq LOC_i \cdot x_i - \sum_{j,j \rightarrow i} LOC_j \cdot z_{ji} \quad \forall i = 0, 1, \dots, n \quad (4.18)$$

$$t_m \leq LOC_0(1 - x_i) + LOC_i \cdot x_i - \sum_{j,j \rightarrow i} LOC_j \cdot z_{ji} \quad \forall i = 0, 1, \dots, n \quad (4.19)$$

$$x_0 = 1 \quad (4.20)$$

$$x_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (4.21)$$

$$z_{ji} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall j \rightarrow i \quad (4.22)$$

$$t_M, t_m, c_M, c_m \in \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (4.23)$$

where Eqs. (4.11), (4.12), (4.16), (4.17), (4.18), (4.19), and (4.23) were added to the single-objective model to add the new objectives.

Eq. (4.11) is the objective of balancing the CC throughout all the extractions after the extract method refactoring is performed, and Eq. (4.12) does the same for balancing the LOC. Constraints (4.16) and (4.17) make c_M the upper bound of the CC of the extracted methods and c_m the lower bound. Similarly, Constraints (4.18) and (4.19) make t_M and t_m the upper and lower bounds of the LOC of the extracted methods, respectively. Minimising the difference between both variables, both for CC and LOC, means that in an optimal solution, these variables become maximums and minimums, respectively.

This model allows a family of seven optimization problems to be solved for each non-empty combination of objectives from Eqs. (4.10)- (4.11). If Objective (4.12) is not used in the model, then Constraints (4.16) and (4.17) might be excluded from it. Similarly, if Objective (4.11) is excluded, then Constraints (4.18) and (4.19) would not be added to this model.

4.3 Multi-objective ILP algorithms

The algorithms implemented to solve the ILP problem introduced in Section 4.2 are presented in this section. First, a weighted sum algorithm has been developed to find the supported solution of each PF. Second, an augmented ε -constraint and a hybrid method have been designed to get all efficient solutions of the multi-objective ILP problem.

4.3.1 Weighted sum algorithm

This algorithm solves a single-objective problem where the objective to optimize is a weighted sum of the original objectives in the multi-objective problem.

Unsupported solutions, i.e., solutions that don't belong to the convex envelope of the PF, are not reached with this algorithm. Furthermore, with the weighted sum algorithm, many runs may be redundant, as numerous combinations of weights can yield the same efficient extreme solution (Mavrotas, 2009). Algorithm 1 shows the implementation of the weighted sum algorithm for p objectives.

4.3.2 Augmented ε -constraint algorithm

An efficient algorithm to solve the multi-objective ILP problem is the one proposed by Mavrotas (2009). It is known as *augmented ε -constraint* or AUGMECON, and it is shown in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 1: Weighted sum algorithm for p objectives

Input: Number of combinations of weights

Output: PF

```
1 for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to Number of combinations of weights do
2    $(w_1, \dots, w_p) \leftarrow$  generate weights for subdivision  $i$ 
3    $z \leftarrow$  solve  $\left\{ \min \left( \sum_{i=1}^p w_i \cdot f_i(x) \right), \text{ subject to } x \in X \right\}$ 
4    $PF = PF \cup \{z\}$ 
5 end
```

This algorithm solves one sub-problem in each iteration, and each solution obtained is guaranteed to be efficient.

Algorithm 2: Augmented ε -constraint (AUGMECON)

Output: PF

```
1  $z \leftarrow$  solve  $\{\min f_2(x), \text{ subject to } x \in X\}$ 
2  $z \leftarrow$  solve  $\{\min f_1(x), \text{ subject to } f_2(x) \leq f_2(z), x \in X\}$ 
3  $PF \leftarrow \{z\}$  // Pareto front
4  $\varepsilon \leftarrow f_1(z) - 1$ 
5 while  $\exists x \in X, f_1(x) \leq \varepsilon$  do
6   Estimate a value for  $\lambda > 0$ 
7    $z \leftarrow$  solve  $\{\min f_2(x) - \lambda \cdot s, \text{ subject to } f_1(x) + s = \varepsilon, x \in X\}$ 
8    $PF = PF \cup \{z\}$ 
9    $\varepsilon \leftarrow f_1(x) - 1$ 
10 end
```

For each iteration, the algorithm sets a positive value for the λ constant, which must be small enough to prevent the algorithm from omitting some of the efficient solutions, and large enough to avoid numerical problems. In general, it is sufficient to take a value of λ in $[10^{-6}, 10^{-3}]$. Chicano et al. (2016) chose to calculate the value of λ at each iteration, taking into account the efficient point obtained previously.

Given a multi-objective optimization problem, the *ideal* point is $ID = (id_1, \dots, id_n)$, where $id_i = \min_{x \in PF} x_i$, and the *nadir* point as $NA = (na_1, \dots, na_n)$, where $na_i = \max_{x \in PF} x_i$.

In this work, λ is calculated as $\lambda = \frac{1}{(f_1(z) - l_1) \cdot 10^{-3}}$, where $l_1 = id_1$ is a lower bound of $\min f_1(x), x \in X$, that is the first component of the ideal point. Variable s is a slack variable.

4.3.3 Hybrid method with *full p-split* algorithm

An efficient algorithm to solve the multi-objective ILP problem proposed in Section 4.2 is a simplification that we made from the MOCO problem-solving algorithm using full p-split (Miguel Ángel Domínguez Ríos, 2022). This simplification is shown in Algorithm 4, and it uses a filter of boxes contained in other boxes, shown in Algorithm 3. Full p-split is a way of decomposing the search space based on the objective space, and it uses an algorithm called *hybrid method* Guddat et al. (1985).

This algorithm splits the objective space and explores it one by one. Each time it finds a new solution inside one box, it is divided, and the boxes that only contain dominated solutions are discarded. The result after each iteration is the number of new boxes equal to the objectives for each solution found in the initial box. Once the first box is divided, the new boxes overlap, but they occupy a lower volume than the initial one. When a new solution is found, all the boxes that include that new solution are split too.

Figure 4.1 shows an example of the first partition of *full p-split*, and it can be found interactively in Zenodo¹. If the algorithm ends, then the complete PF is obtained, including unsupported solutions. This is the great advantage of the algorithm, as it can not only find all solutions for a convex PF, but also for a PF that has unsupported solutions.

To solve the multi-objective problem, Algorithm 4 takes as input the initial box, that is, the whole objective space. One example for an initial box with $NA = (20, 15, 10)$ is depicted in Figure 4.1a. It finds the complete PF by applying the multi-objective ILP model to each box obtained. An example of the first iteration of *full p-split* is depicted in Figure 4.1b. As a result of the *full p-split*, one box may contain another one, so lines 4 – 18 of Algorithm 3 iterate over all pairs of boxes and eliminate those boxes that are contained in larger boxes.

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15682834>

- (a) Box $\mathbf{B} = [(0, 0, 0), (20, 15, 10)]$, with non-dominated solution $z = (5, 5, 5)$.
- (b) After applying *full-p-split*: $\mathbf{B}_1 = [(5, 15, 10)]$, $\mathbf{B}_2 = [(20, 5, 10)]$, $\mathbf{B}_3 = [(20, 15, 5)]$. The lower bounds of the boxes are all $ID = [(0, 0, 0)]$.

Figure 4.1: Partitioning a box using *full-p-split*.

Algorithm 3: RE (Redundancy elimination)

Input: \mathcal{U}, z // Set of boxes and solution found

Output: \mathcal{U} // New boxes set

- 1 $\mathfrak{R} \leftarrow \{u \in \mathcal{U} : z < u\}$ // Boxes that contain z
- 2 **for** $j \in 1, \dots, p$ **do**
- 3 $\mathfrak{D}_j \leftarrow \{u \in \mathcal{U} : z_j = u_j \wedge z_k < u_k, \forall k \neq j\}$
- 4 $\mathfrak{F}_j \leftarrow \emptyset$
- 5 **end**
- 6 **for** $u \in \mathfrak{R}$ **do**
- 7 **for** $j \in 1, \dots, p$ **do**
- 8 $\mathfrak{F}_j \leftarrow \mathfrak{F}_j \cup \{(u_1, \dots, u_{j-1}, z_j, u_{j+1}, \dots, u_p)\}$
- 9 **end**
- 10 **end**
- 11 **for** $j \in 1, \dots, p$ **do**
- 12 $\mathfrak{F}_j \leftarrow \{z' \in \mathfrak{F}_j : z' \not\leq u', \forall u' \in \mathfrak{F}_j \cup \mathfrak{D}_j - \{z'\}\}$ // Filter redundant boxes
- 13 **end**
- 14 $\mathcal{U} \leftarrow (\mathcal{U} - \mathfrak{R}) \cup \left(\bigcup_{j=1}^p \mathfrak{F}_j \right)$

Algorithm 4: Hybrid Method using *full p-split*

Input: B_0

Output: PF

1 $PF \leftarrow \emptyset$

2 $\mathcal{U} \leftarrow [B_0]$

3 $P(u) \equiv \left\{ \min \left(\sum_{i=1}^p f_i(x) \right), \text{ subject to } f(x) \leq u, x \in \mathcal{X} \right\}$

4 **while** ($\mathcal{U} \neq \emptyset$) **do**

5 $B \leftarrow \mathcal{U}_{first}$

6 **if** ($P(B)$ has solution) **then**

7 $x^* \leftarrow$ Optimal solution of $P(B)$

8 $PF \leftarrow PF \cup \{f(x^*)\}$

9 $\mathcal{U} \leftarrow \text{FCB}(\mathcal{U}, f(x^*))$

10 **else**

11 $\mathcal{U} \leftarrow \mathcal{U} - B$

12 **end**

13 **end**

5

Implementation

This chapter shows the implementation of the ILP CC reducer tool at method level. It describes the requirements of the tool, its architecture, and its implementation.

Figure 5.1 shows the functional overview of the proposed ILP CC reducer tool. Firstly, the tool might receive a CSV file containing the *refactoring cache of a method*, that is, a list of extract method refactoring opportunities associated with a method to reduce its CC. This file contains relevant information about candidate code extractions over the original method. The refactoring cache of a method is generated from the tool developed by [Saborido et al. \(2022\)](#). Second, the refactoring cache processing module automatically generates the following four CSV files, which are needed for the ILP CC reducer module:

- `MethodName1_extractions.csv`. It stores the index of each feasible extraction (i), the LOC_i of the extraction, and the $NMCC_i$ of each extraction. There is a fourth column that is not used at the moment, but could be helpful for future work. That column stores the number of parameters that each feasible extraction would need when called.
- `MethodName1_nested.csv`. It stores the indexes of the child extractions (j), the indexes of their parents (i), and the $CCR_{j \rightarrow i}$ of each relationship.
- `MethodName1_conflict.csv`. It stores the extractions in conflict. The conflict extractions are related in pairs in the two columns of the file.
- `MethodName1_feasible_extractions_offsets.csv`. It stores the index of each extraction (i), its start offset, and its end offset. These offsets are used to indicate the start and end positions of code extractions within the original file.

¹MethodName is the name of the method under processing and not the literal “MethodName”.

Thirdly, using the generated CSV files, the ILP CC reducer module models the ILP optimization problem and solves it. This module takes the following inputs from the user:

1. **Number of objectives.** Sets the number of objectives to consider (from one to three).
2. **Algorithm.** The algorithm selected for solving the ILP problem.
 - For the single-objective ILP problem, `ObtainResultsAlgorithm` is the only possible value (this is also the default value for single-objective optimization).
 - For multi-objective optimization ILP problems, three algorithms are available:
 - (a) `WeightedSumAlgorithm`, where the user can specify:
 - i. The weights for the objectives. It must be specified as w_1, w_2 (for two objectives) or w_1, w_2, w_3 (for three objectives).
 - ii. The number of combinations of weights. It must be specified as s .
 - (b) `EpsilonConstraintAlgorithm` if the user wants to execute ϵ -constraint algorithm.
 - (c) `HybridMethodAlgorithm` if the user wants to execute the hybrid method algorithm.
3. **Threshold.** Sets the maximum CC that all extractions must have after the extraction has been performed, including the original method.
4. **Objectives list.** An ordered list of the objectives: *EXTRACTIONS*, *CC*, and *LOC* (for number of code extractions, balancing of CC among extractions, and balancing LOC, respectively). If this list is not provided, the default ordered list is `extractions`, `extractions` and `CC`, or `extractions`, `CC` and `LOC`, for one, two, or three objectives, respectively. This input is optional.

The tool creates the corresponding model according to the parameters specified in the input. As shown in Figure 5.1, the output is a CSV file with the set of optimal solutions, statistics of each solution, and different visual content depending on the selected algorithm. One optimal solution to the ILP problem is a sequence of extractions that has a given impact on the user-specified objectives and that reduces the CC of the initial method below the given threshold.

The ILP CC reducer tool is developed in Python, using Pyomo to implement the ILP problem modelling. The solver used for the resolution of the built ILP model is CPLEX. Pyomo²

²<https://pyomo.readthedocs.io/en/stable/> (last accessed June 2025)

Figure 5.1: Overview of the proposed ILP CC reducer tool. *Objectives list is optional.

is an open-source Algebraic Modelling Language (AML) used for mathematical optimization. An AML is a language for expressing optimization models concisely and naturally, avoiding implementation details. It aims to standardize the way optimization problems are modelled, making it easier to exchange models between different users and communities. CPLEX³ is a prescriptive analytics solution that accelerates the development and implementation of decision optimization models using mathematical and constraint programming. It has excellent compatibility with Python. Moreover, it is a software with a long history of development, which has allowed it to reach a high degree of maturity, robustness, and efficiency in the resolution of optimisation problems.

The core of the ILP CC reducer tool is the ILP CC reducer module. Its architecture is shown in Figure 5.2, which is organised into three main submodules:

1. **Models**, defining the following optimization models:
 - `ILPmodel` for single-objective ILP problems.
 - `MO-ILPmodel` for multi-objective ILP problems.
2. **Algorithms**, implementing the following optimization strategies:
 - `ObtainResultsAlgorithm`. This algorithm returns the solutions for the single-objective ILP model (Saborido et al., 2024).

³<https://www.ibm.com/es-es/products/ilog-cplex-optimization-studio> (last accessed June 2025)

- **WeightedSumAlgorithm.** Weighted sum algorithms for two and three objectives. This was the initial algorithm used to generate a sweep through the objective space. They are useful to get an idea of the optimal solutions, although not all non-dominated ones may be obtained, as unsupported solutions cannot be obtained with this algorithm.
 - **EpsilonConstraintAlgorithm.** This algorithm was implemented based on the *augmented ε -constraint* algorithm, or AUGMECON, proposed by Mavrotas (2009) (see Section 4.3.2). All non-dominated solutions are obtained if the algorithm ends.
 - **HybridMethodAlgorithm.** This algorithm uses the *full- p -split* objective space partition to find all optimal solutions. This algorithm is a simplification of the *Algorithm 3* proposed by Miguel Ángel Domínguez Ríos (2022) (see Section 4.3.3). All non-dominated solutions are obtained if the algorithm ends.
3. **ILPengine.** The main component that connects models and algorithms and manages the execution flow.

The rest of the modules presented in Figure 5.2 are:

- **Utils.** Auxiliary tools for managing input and output data.
- **original_method / refactored_method.** Contain the original and refactored methods from a functional perspective. They are the input and output of the module, respectively.
- **Pyomo:** The modelling framework used to build the mathematical models.
- **CPLEX.** Used as the solver for ILP problems.

The ILP CC reducer module class diagram is represented in Figure 5.3. It is structured around three core components. The **ILPengine** class orchestrates the overall workflow by loading data, retrieving available algorithms, and applying a chosen algorithm to a given instance. Algorithms are defined through an abstract **Algorithm** class, which is extended by concrete implementations, including the ones specified in Figure 5.2. The modelling layer includes the **MultiobjectiveILPmodel**, which defines various objective functions, weighted sum aggregations, and epsilon-constraint formulations, for both two and three-objective problems, to implement the novel multi-objective model described in Chapter 4. The **general_utils** module provides support functions such as modifying model components, solving instances,

Figure 5.2: Architecture of the ILP CC reducer module.

printing results, managing output data, and generating weight vectors. The tool is executed via the `main.py` script, which integrates all components in a coordinated pipeline. The complete code is available in Zenodo⁴.

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15682834>

Figure 5.3: Class diagram for the ILP CC reducer module.

6

Empirical validation

Since the ILP problem is parametrizable, and different solutions can be obtained depending on the combination of objectives and the number of objectives selected, in this chapter, only the combination of **extractions** and **CC** objectives is solved for two objectives for reasons of space. The rest of the combinations of objectives can be found in our replication package (see Section 1.5). For three objectives, the problem is solved with the order of **extractions**, **CC**, and **LOC**, but the order of objectives does not alter the result.

This chapter shows the results obtained for the hybrid method algorithm with *full p-split*, chosen for its accuracy and versatility. It was used to solve the multi-objective ILP problem for ten methods from an industry project from the Ayesa company and 121 methods selected from nine open-source projects. All result plots and PF in three dimensions can also be viewed interactively in the replication package.

6.1 Experimental setup

We conducted the experiments on a Dell Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6240R CPU machine with 220 GB of RAM and 96 cores, running the Ubuntu operating system. We used PyCharm Community Edition 2025.1. We set the cognitive complexity threshold to the default value proposed by SonarQube ($\tau = 15$). AST processing and Extract Method refactorings were performed through Eclipse JDT version 3.31.0 and Eclipse LTK version 3.10.0. To solve ILP optimization problems, we used the Pyomo library for modelling and IBM ILOG CPLEX Optimization Studio V22.1.1 through the IBM Academic Initiative for solving each ILP model.

6.2 Objects of study

To study the performance of the proposed approach, several methods, both from open-source projects and industry projects from Ayesa, have been chosen. Although the ILP CC reducer tool is configurable and different results can be obtained by varying both the number of objectives and the algorithm to be used, we consider the augmented ε -constraint algorithm described in Algorithm 2, and the hybrid method algorithm described in Algorithm 4.

6.2.1 Ayesa projects

Ayesa is a global provider of technological and engineering services, with 13,000 professionals and direct presence in 24 countries in Europe, America, Africa, Asia, and Oceania. They develop and implement digital solutions for companies and public administrations, applying the latest technologies to the design and supervision of infrastructures. They have teams specialised in more than 70 disciplines and certified in market-leading technologies, working in the fields of digital administration, health, industry, consumer, banking, insurance, telco and media, energy and utilities, transport, building and urban planning, resources and the environment. In its vocation to be a global, creative, technology-driven, and human-centric company, at Ayesa they are committed to talent, through diversity and inclusion, as well as sustainability, as a hallmark and lever for innovation.

Ten methods from an industry project of Ayesa are studied. As Ayesa's code is confidential, the PF's graphs are shown, but no more information about the code is provided.

6.2.2 Open-source projects

Nine open-source projects were selected: two popular frameworks for multi-objective optimization, five platform components to accelerate the development of smart solutions, and two popular open-source projects with more than 10,000 stars and forked more than 900 times. These open-source projects are shown in Table 6.1. It is also specified the commit hash for each open-source project.

The 121 methods selected from the nine open-source projects are unequivocally presented in Table B.1. The complete table can also be found in our replication package¹.

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15682834>

Table 6.1: Open-source projects and their respective commits used for experimentation.

Project	Commit	Number of issues considered
ByteCode	55bfc32	20
Cybercaptor	b6b1f10	19
FastJson	93d8c01e9	21
Fiware-Commons	f83b342	3
IoTBroker	98eeceb	10
Jedis	cfc227f7	3
jMetal	e6baf75aa	14
Knowage-core	dfed28a869	15
MOEA-Framework	223393fd	16

6.3 Results

This section shows the results obtained for two objectives (extractions and CC) and for three objectives (extractions, CC, and LOC), both for Ayesa projects and the nine open-source projects under study.

The results obtained are represented in several ways for each of the methods under study. For two-objective problems, the complete PF in two dimensions is obtained and presented. For three-objective problems, the results obtained are presented through parallel coordinate plots, by tables showing the results, numerically, and by PF plots in three dimensions. A parallel coordinates plot is an intuitive way of representing results used for multivariate data, i.e., multiple variables or dimensions. It is a practical way of representing the solutions of the PF, because it shows the results for each objective function and links them by straight lines so that all solutions can be observed simultaneously.

All results obtained have no stop criteria. If the algorithm used ends, the whole PF is obtained.

We compute hypervolume (HV) as a reference for future applications that attempt to solve the same problem with heuristic algorithms, so that both can be compared. HV is the n -dimensional space that is “contained” by a set of points (Bradstreet, 2011). It contains a lot of mathematical properties and provides a single scalar value that simultaneously reflects both the diversity of the solutions along the PF and their proximity (convergence) to the actual

Pareto-optimal front.

The HV has been normalized to ensure comparability across different instances and objective scales. As a result, reported values are bounded between zero and one. The normalization process used divided the absolute HV obtained with the `pymoo` library by the total volume obtained from the cube defined between the ideal and the reference points.

6.3.1 Two objectives' results

Every solution in the PF obtained using the hybrid method algorithm for two objectives (extractions and CC) can be represented with a 2D representation. The order of the objectives does not change the solution.

The results for the remaining objective combinations, including the number of extractions and LOC difference, as well as the combination of CC difference and LOC difference objectives, are not presented in this document to reduce its size. Still, they can be found in Zenodo².

6.3.1.1 Ayesa's results for two objectives

Table 6.2 presents a summary of the performance of each method according to the HV metric. These include the identifier assigned to each method, the total number of solutions obtained, and the reference point employed during evaluation. To provide a reference of the solution quality for future results, we also report the normalized HV covered by the solutions obtained for each method under study, along with the median and inter-quartile range (*IQR*) obtained for each objective under study. The specified reference point in Table 6.2 is the nadir point of the obtained PF for each method after adding one unit to the objective function values, $Reference = (na_1 + 1, \dots, na_n + 1)$. The HV obtained for the method that has only one solution is 1.

Table 6.2 presents a summary of the performance of the hybrid method algorithm for each Ayesa method according to the HV metric.

The fifth Ayesa's method studied for two objectives is a non-convex PF. It is depicted in Figure 6.1, and as can be observed, the second solution, **s2**, could not be reached with linear combinations of the two objectives studied. The number of extractions varies from 2 to 6 across the different solutions obtained, whereas for CC difference, the variation goes from 0 to 2. This means that, for the worst case in the CC difference objective, the difference of CC

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15682834>

Table 6.2: Results for two objectives obtained for methods under study in industry projects from Ayesa. Each column represents, respectively, the order of each method, the number of solutions obtained for the method, and the reference point used for the method (*Extractions (E)*, *CC (C)*) to compute the HV, normalized HV (N-HV), and the median and inter-quartile range (*IQR*) for the two objective functions.

Ayesa's method	No. sol	Reference (E,C)	N-HV	Extractions		CC	
				<i>Median</i>	<i>IQR</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>IQR</i>
1st	1	(3,14)	1.00	2.0	0.0	13.0	0.0
2nd	2	(4,9)	0.57	2.5	0.5	5.0	3.0
3rd	2	(4,2)	0.75	2.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
4th	2	(5,6)	0.67	3.0	1.0	4.5	0.5
5th	3	(7,3)	0.53	5.0	2.0	1.0	1.0
6th	3	(8,4)	0.67	3.0	2.5	2.0	1.0
7th	3	(7,6)	0.72	3.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
8th	2	(6,4)	0.50	3.5	1.5	2.0	1.0
9th	3	(8,6)	0.60	5.0	2.0	3.0	1.5
10th	2	(8,3)	0.58	4.5	2.5	1.5	0.5

among the extractions of code obtained varies at most 2, and the CC does not vary for the best case.

6.3.1.2 Open-source methods' results for two objectives

Table B.3 in Appendix B presents the same summary as the one for Ayesa's project, but in this case, the results are the ones obtained for the nine open-source projects of Table 6.1.

The two-dimensional PF selected to be shown in this case (out of the 121 methods under study from open-source projects) is depicted in Figure 6.2. Again, this PF has an unsupported solution, that is the solution **s3**. The number of extractions for each solution is 8, 10, 15, and 17 extractions, with a difference of CC of 11, 8, 7 and 6, respectively.

Figure 6.1: 2D PF obtained by the hybrid method algorithm for two objectives for the fifth Ayesa's method.

6.3.2 Three objectives' results

Every solution from the PF obtained from the hybrid method algorithm for three objectives (extractions, CC, and LOC) can be represented with parallel coordinates, as well as directly in a 3D representation. In any case, the order of the objectives does not change the solution.

6.3.2.1 Ayesa's results for three objectives

Table 6.3 presents a summary of the performance of the hybrid method algorithm for each Ayesa method according to the HV metric. In the same way that the results were presented for two objectives, they are shown for three objectives, also adding the results for the LOC balancing.

Two instances out of the ten studied methods from Ayesa's project are shown in Figures 6.3 and 6.4. For each figure, the first subfigure corresponds to the parallel coordinates plot of each PF, the second one is the list of Pareto optimal solutions obtained, and the third is a visualization of the obtained PF in three dimensions. All plots can be found in Zenodo³.

As can be observed in Figure 6.3, the number of extractions varies from 2 to 8 across the

³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15682834>

Figure 6.2: PF obtained by the epsilon constraint algorithm for the `seekObjectToField(long[])` method from the `JSONScanner` class in the `fastjson` project.

different solutions obtained. For CC difference, the variation goes from 1 to 5. Similarly, the LOC difference between the methods obtained after the extraction varies at most 3 in the best case for the LOC difference, and 11 in the worst case.

As shown in Figure 6.4, this method is the one with the maximum number of solutions obtained of all those that have been depicted from Ayesa. Its normalized HV is also the highest in Table 6.3.

6.3.2.2 Open-source methods' results for three objectives

Finally, the results obtained for three objectives for the methods selected from the nine open-source projects are shown in Table B.3. The structure is the same as the one in Table 6.3. For these methods, the number of solutions shown is significant because 12% of the studied methods have only one solution. Therefore, in these cases, there is no conflict between the three objectives under study. For these cases (with only one solution), the HV obtained is one.

The solutions for three objectives obtained for the running example in Figure 1.1 are presented in Figure 6.5.

Table 6.3: Results obtained for three objectives for methods under study in industry projects from Ayesa. Each column represents, respectively, the order of each method, the number of solutions obtained for the method, and the reference point used for the method (*Extractions (E)*, *CC (C)*, *LOC (L)*) to compute the HV, normalized HV (N-HV), and the median and inter-quartile range (*IQR*) for the three objective functions.

Ayesa's method	No. sol	Reference (<i>E,C,L</i>)	N-HV	Extractions		CC		LOC	
				Median	IQR	Median	IQR	Median	IQR
1st	1	(3,14,19)	1.00	2.0	0.00	13.0	0.00	18.0	0.00
2nd	2	(4,9,26)	0.51	2.5	0.50	5.0	3.00	18.5	6.50
3rd	2	(4,2,11)	0.52	2.5	0.50	0.5	0.50	5.5	4.50
4th	4	(8,6,21)	0.57	5.0	2.75	4.0	0.25	16.5	5.25
5th	4	(9,3,13)	0.41	5.5	2.25	1.0	0.50	8.0	5.75
6th	5	(9,4,6)	0.49	4.0	4.00	2.0	0.00	4.0	1.00
7th	6	(8,6,25)	0.33	3.5	2.50	2.5	1.75	18.5	4.75
8th	7	(9,6,12)	0.66	5.0	1.50	2.0	2.00	5.0	3.00
9th	8	(11,6,13)	0.49	7.0	2.50	3.0	0.25	5.5	7.00
10th	20	(12,11,45)	0.79	5.5	3.25	3.5	3.25	9.5	10.00

If the solution that best balances LOC is chosen, i.e., the second solution (**s2** in Figure 6.5), the corresponding extractions are the ones in Figure B.1, and its corresponding AST version of the refactoring is the one in Figure B.2. As can be seen in Figure B.1, there are three extractions taking into account the original method, and they are one nested in the other. The CC of each method, respectively, is 2, 5, and 4, so the difference between the maximum and minimum CC of all methods after the extractions have been performed is $5 - 2 = 3$. Similarly, the LOC of each resulting method is 7, 8, and 8, so the difference between the maximum and minimum LOC of all methods after the refactoring is $8 - 7 = 1$.

(a) Parallel coordinates.

Objective \ Solution	Extractions	CC _{diff}	LOC _{diff}
s1	6	1	5
s2	7	4	3
s3	5	2	8
s4	2	3	5
s5	5	1	11
s6	5	5	4
s7	8	2	3

(b) Table.

(c) 3D PF visualization.

Figure 6.3: 3D PF obtained by the hybrid method algorithm for three objectives for the eighth Ayesa's method.

(a) Parallel coordinates.

Objective Solution	<i>Extractions</i>	<i>CC_{diff}</i>	<i>LOC_{diff}</i>
s1	9	3	4
s2	2	4	18
s3	5	3	6
s4	10	2	6
s5	4	2	19
s6	4	6	10
s7	3	4	16
s8	6	7	2
s9	2	2	44
s10	7	4	3
s11	7	2	9
s12	3	10	1
s13	7	1	25
s14	11	3	3
s15	6	4	5
s16	8	1	11
s17	5	6	3
s18	4	5	13
s19	6	2	10
s20	3	9	13

(b) Table.

(c) 3D PF visualization.

Figure 6.4: 3D PF obtained by the hybrid method algorithm for three objectives for the tenth Ayesa's method.

(a) Parallel coordinates.

Objective \ Solution	<i>Extractions</i>	<i>CC_{diff}</i>	<i>LOC_{diff}</i>
s1	2	2	3
s2	3	3	1
s3	6	1	6
s4	8	1	4
s5	4	2	2

(b) Table.

(c) 3D PF visualization.

Figure 6.5: routeAPacketTo method result from Host class in cybercaptor-server project. This is the solution for the method used for the running example in Figure 2.7.

7

Conclusion and future work

This chapter concludes by studying the results of experiments conducted with the ILP CC reducer tool on real software projects and states the future work.

7.1 Conclusion

During the development of this Master's thesis, a new multi-objective ILP formulation for reducing software CC has been developed, allowing the minimization of the number of code extractions while balancing the LOC and CC of extracted methods.

A novel software tool has also been designed and developed to ease the CC reduction of software. This tool integrates several multi-objective ILP problem-solving algorithms, including an ε -constraint algorithm and a hybrid method algorithm, which traverse the entire objective space and can approximate the complete Pareto front. The proposed multi-objective ILP model and the software tool have been validated using a benchmark of 121 methods from nine open-source projects and 10 from an industrial software project in Java. A set of efficient solutions has been obtained for each of them. Regarding the solver used, CPLEX has high computational efficiency and uses advanced algorithms that enable large and complex problems to be solved quickly and accurately. This advantage allows the developed tool to be included in continuous software integration processes. Thus, the objectives set for this Master's thesis have been met.

In contrast, one limitation of the work is that CPLEX is not free, and its commercial licence is expensive. In some cases, such as for method number 97 from open-source projects

solved for two objectives, no solution has been obtained. For now, no exhaustive record of the methods that cannot be solved has been made.

7.2 Future work

As future work, three main lines of development are proposed to extend and enrich this work. First, as assigning a representative name to the extractions is crucial, we can integrate the use of LLMs for methods naming. The more extractions are performed, the more challenging the method name assignment is. The key is how to prompt the model to indicate all the requirements needed to infer method names adequately. The application of changes to the source code has not yet been automated. This task will be included as future work and completed in the ILP CC reducer tool. Theoretically, we will have a Java programme that will read the output CSV to apply the extractions. Second, it is planned to design and conduct a series of surveys targeting expert or semi-expert users to assess the perceived quality and usefulness of the results generated by the proposed multi-objective ILP approach. The responses will be systematically compared with those from previous evaluations based on the single-objective ILP approach developed by [Saborido et al. \(2024\)](#). The purpose of this comparative study is not only to validate the improvements introduced by the multi-objective ILP formulation but also to gather qualitative insights into user preferences and expectations, to guide future iterations of the system. Finally, it is intended to study the scalability of the multi-objective ILP model, as adding numerous constraints can lead to an increase in execution time that makes the model unrunnable. In this case, the possibility of solving the model presented in this Master's thesis through other optimization techniques will be studied.

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Appendix A.0

User manual

User manual for the ILP CC reducer tool: multi-objective Integer Linear Programming approach for Automatic Software Cognitive Complexity Reduction.

A.1 ILP Model Engine

This project provides a command-line engine for solving ILP (Integer Linear Programming) problems related to reducing cognitive complexity, CC, in Java code refactorings at the method level. The tool supports solving both single-objective and multi-objective ILP instances using various algorithms and configurations.

A.2 Requirements

- [Python 3.9+](#)
- [CPLEX](#)

The library has been tested in Linux (Mint and Ubuntu) and Windows 11.

A.3 Download and Installation

1. Install [Python 3.9+](#)
2. Download/Clone the [repository](#) and enter the main directory.
3. Create a virtual environment: `python -m venv env`.
4. Activate the environment:

- In Linux: `source env/bin/activate`
 - In Windows: `.\env\Scripts\Activate`
- ** In case you are running Ubuntu, please install the package `python3-dev` with the command `sudo apt update && sudo apt install python3-dev` and update `wheel` and `setuptools` with the command `pip install --upgrade pip wheel setuptools` right after step 4.

5. Install the dependencies: `pip install -r requirements.txt`.

A.4 Overview

The main purpose of this application is to automate the generation and resolution of ILP models designed to **optimize code refactorings**. The models aim to **minimize**:

1. The number of extractions (refactorings).
2. The difference between the maximum and minimum **cognitive complexity**, CC, across all resulting extractions.
3. The difference between the maximum and minimum **lines of code**, LOC, across all resulting extractions.

A.5 Problem Context

Given a Java method and its corresponding **refactoring cache**, the system builds ILP model instances to explore different refactoring strategies. These models are then solved with one of several available algorithms.

The results may vary:

- A **.csv file** and a corresponding **.lp file** for **single-objective** ILP.
- For **multi-objective** problems (2 or 3 objectives), a set of solutions using:
 - **Weighted sum** (single or multiple combinations).
 - **Augmented ε -constraint**.
 - A **hybrid method algorithm**.

A.6 Getting Started

To run the main engine:

```
python main.py [ARGUMENTS]
```

A.6.1 Arguments

Arguments available in this tool are summarized in Table A.1.

A.6.2 Output Types

Depending on the model and input configuration, the application can generate:

- For **single-objective ILP**:
 - A `.CSV` file containing the solution.
 - An `.lp` file representing the ILP model for each instance.
- For **multi-objective ILP** (2 or 3 objectives):
 - A set of non-dominated solutions (Pareto front), either:
 - * via **weighted sum**:
 - using a sweep over weight combinations (`--subdivisions`), or
 - with a specific combination (`--weights`).
 - * via **augmented ε -constraint** algorithm (`-algorithm`):
 - CSV file with results.
 - Concrete model.
 - Output data with the solution for each Java method.
 - * via a **hybrid objective-space exploration algorithm**:
 - CSV file with results.
 - Concrete model.
 - Output data with the solution for each Java method.
 - Reference point.
 - Plot in case of requested.

A.7 Objectives (CC Metrics)

The optimization process focuses on refactoring Java methods by minimizing the following CC metrics:

1. Number of Extractions:

- The total number of code extractions performed.
 - *Goal:* Minimize to keep changes limited.

2. Complexity Range:

- Difference between the highest and lowest CC values among extractions.
 - *Goal:* Minimize to ensure balanced complexity across parts.

3. LOC Range:

- Difference between the largest and smallest number of LOC among extracted parts.
 - *Goal:* Minimize to obtain balanced code lengths.

A.8 Additional Script

A secondary `input_files_main.py` located in `ILP_data_from_refactoring_cache` folder is used to **generate ILP input files** from a refactoring cache. This cache must be generated beforehand by another tool that analyses Java code.

The **arguments** for this file are the `input_folder` and `output_folder`.

A.9 Examples

Some examples of the use of the tool are:

```
python main.py
  -n 3
  -i ./instances/my_instance
  -a HybridMethodForThreeObj
  -t 15 -o seq,loc,cc --plot
```

```
python main.py
    -n 2
    -i ./instances/my_instance
    -a WeightedSumAlgorithm2obj
    -t 2 -s 6 -o seq,loc
```

```
python input_files_main.py
    ./input_folder
    ./output_folder
```

A.10 Project Structure

The project structure is the following:

```
ILP-CC-reducer-tool
├─ ILP_data_from_refactoring_cache
│  ├─ dataset_refactoring_caches
│  ├─ utils
│  │  ├─ dataset.py
│  │  ├─ offsets.py
│  │  └─ refactoring_cache.py
│  ├─ __init__.py
│  ├─ input_files_main.py
│  └─ README.md
├─ ILP_CC_reducer
│  ├─ algorithm
│  │  ├─ __init__.py
│  │  └─ algorithm.py
│  ├─ algorithms
│  │  ├─ __init__.py
│  │  ├─ e_constraint_two_objs.py
│  │  ├─ hybrid_method_three_objs.py
│  │  ├─ obtain_results.py
│  │  └─ weighted_sum.py
```

```
| | └─ weighted_sum_two_objs.py
| └─ models
| | └─ __init__.py
| | └─ ILPmodelRsain.py
| | └─ multiobjILPmodel.py
| └─ operations
|   └─ __init__.py
|   └─ ILP_engine.py
└─ general_utils.py
└─ main.py
└─ README.md
└─ requirements.txt
```

Table A.1: Arguments available for the multi-objective ILP reducer tool.

Argument	Description
-f, --file	Path to a .ini file containing all parameters.
-n, --num_of_objectives	Number of objectives to be considered: 1, 2 or 3.
-i, --instance	Path to the model instance. For multi-objective, this should be a folder containing three .CSV files.
-a, --algorithm	Algorithm to use for solving multi-objective problems. Must be one of: ['ObtainResultsAlgorithm', 'WeightedSumAlgorithm', 'EpsilonConstraintAlgorithm', 'HybridMethodAlgorithm'].
-t, --tau	Threshold (τ) used in optimization (e.g., for ε -constraint).
-s, --subdivisions	Number of subdivisions for generating weighted combinations.
-w, --weights	Specific weights for weighted sum: w1,w2,w3.
-o, --objectives	List of objectives to minimize, e.g., obj1,obj2 or obj1,obj2,obj3.
--plot	Plot the result of a specific experiment.
--3dPF	Plot the 3D PF of the given result.
--all_plots	Plot all results in the given directory.
--all_3dPF	Plot all 3D PFs in a given directory.
--statistics	Generate a CSV file with statistics for all results in the given directory.
--input	Input directory for results (used for plotting/statistics). Defaults to output/results.
--output	Output directory for plots/statistics. Defaults to output/plots_and_statistics.
--save	Save current configuration to a .ini file.

Appendix B.0

Open-source projects additional information

This appendix shows all the tables referred to in Chapter 6, which for reasons of space are more conveniently consulted here.

Table B.1 displays the index assigned to each method, the project to which it belongs, the class within the project where it can be found, and its name. Due to space constraints, each class is simplified and only the beginning and the end of the route are shown, connected by ellipses. Tables B.2 and B.3 are described in Sub-subsections 6.3.1.2 and 6.3.2.2, respectively.

If the solution that best balances LOC in Figure 6.5 is chosen, i.e., the second solution (s2), the corresponding extractions are the ones in Figure B.1, and its corresponding AST version of the refactoring is the one in Figure B.2. These figures are referred to in Sub-subsection 6.3.2.2.

Table B.1: Methods selected from the nine open-source projects studied.

ID	project	class	method
1	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...ASMResourceUtil.java	renameClassNode
2	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...ASMResourceUtil.java	renameFieldNode
3	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...ASMResourceUtil.java	renameMethodNode
4	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...Boot.java	downloadZipsOnly
5	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...BytecodeViewer.java	compile
6	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...CommandLineInput.java	parseCommandLine
7	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...ProcyonDecompiler.java	doSaveJarDecompiled
8	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...ResourceListItemIconRenderer.java	getTreeCellRendererComponent
9	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...ReplaceStrings.java	scanClassNode
10	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the...ViewAPKAndroidPermissions.java	execute
11	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...ZStringArrayDecrypter.java	execute
12	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...impl.APKExport.java	promptForExport
13	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...DirectoryResourceImporter.java	open
14	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...util.BootCheck.java	failSafeLoadLibraries
15	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...util.FileDrop.java	FileDrop
16	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...util.JarUtils.java	importArchiveA
17	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...util.JarUtils.java	importArchiveB
18	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...util.JTextAreaUtils.java	search

19	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...util.MethodParser.java	findNearestMethod
20	bytecode-viewer	src.main.java.the.bytecode...util.SecurityMan.java	checkExec
21	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware...AttackGraph.java	getRelatedTopologyGraph
22	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware...AttackPath.java	getLeavesThatCanBeRemediated
23	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware...AttackPath.java	getRemediationActions
24	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware...AttackPath.java	getRemediationAction
25	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware...AttackPath.java	getRemediationActionForLeaf
26	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware...AttackPath.java	leavesMandatoryForVertex
27	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware...AttackPath.java	printListRemediations
28	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware...AttackPath.java	remediateLeaf
29	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware...MulvalAttackGraph.java	addArcsAndVerticesFromDomElement
30	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware...Vertex.java	getRelatedMachine
31	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware.cybercaptor...AttackPaths.java	exploreAttackPath
32	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware.cybercaptor...Interface.java	mergeTwoInterfaces
33	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware.cybercaptor...Host.java	equals
34	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware.cybercaptor...Host.java	hostThatPreventToSendAPacket
35	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware.cybercaptor...Host.java	routeAPacketTo
36	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware.cybercaptor...Topology.java	clone
37	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware.cybercaptor...Topology.java	mergeTwoHosts
38	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware.cybercaptor...Topology.java	sendAPacketOnARoute

39	cybercaptor-server	src.main.java.org.fiware.cybercaptor...CPE.java	populateCPECVEDatabase	
40	fastjson	src.main.java.com...JSON.java	toJSON	
41	fastjson	src.main.java.com...JSONPath.java	buildArraySegement	
42	fastjson	src.main.java.com...JSONPath.java	extract(JSONPath-DefaultJSONParser-Context)	
43	fastjson	src.main.java.com...JSONPath.java	getItem	
44	fastjson	src.main.java.com...JSONPath.java	getPropertyValue	
45	fastjson	src.main.java.com...JSONPath.java	paths	
46	fastjson	src.main.java.com...JSONPath.java	readSegement	
47	fastjson	src.main.java.com...AbstractDateDeserializer.java	deserialize	
48	fastjson	src.main.java.com...DefaultFieldDeserializer.java	parseField	
∞	49	fastjson	src.main.java.com...parser.deserializer.Jdk8DateCodec.java	parseDateTime
50	fastjson	src.main.java.com...parser.deserializer.Jdk8DateCodec.java	parseLocalDate	
51	fastjson	src.main.java.com...parser.deserializer.Jdk8DateCodec.java	parseZonedDateTime	
52	fastjson	src.main.java.com...parser.JSONLexerBase.java	integerValue	
53	fastjson	src.main.java.com...parser.JSONLexerBase.java	scanFieldStringArray	
54	fastjson	src.main.java.com...parser.JSONLexerBase.java	scanNumber	
55	fastjson	src.main.java.com...parser.JSONScanner.java	seekObjectToField(long[])	
56	fastjson	src.main.java.com...serializer.JodaCodec.java	parseDateTime	
57	fastjson	src.main.java.com...serializer.PrimitiveArraySerializer.java	write	
58	fastjson	src.main.java.com...util.TypeUtils.java	cast(Object-Class-T-ParserConfig)	
59	fastjson	src.main.java.com...util.TypeUtils.java	castToDate	

60	fastjson	src.main.java.com...util.TypeUtils.java	castToJavaBean
61	fiware-commons	src.main.java.com...OpenStackKeystoneV2.java	parseEndpoint
62	fiware-commons	src.main.java.com...OpenStackKeystoneV2.java	parseRegionNames
63	fiware-commons	src.main.java.com...OpenStackKeystoneV3.java	parseRegionNames
64	iotbroker	src.main.java.com...amqp.AmqpClient.java	processAttach
65	iotbroker	src.main.java.com...amqp.net.AMQPDecoder.java	decode
66	iotbroker	src.main.java.com...amqp.TimersMap.java	store
67	iotbroker	src.main.java.com...coap.CoapClient.java	packetReceived
68	iotbroker	src.main.java.com...mqtt.MqttClient.java	processSuback
69	iotbroker	src.main.java.com...mqtt.net.MQDecoder.java	decode
70	iotbroker	src.main.java.com...mqtt.TimersMap.java	store
71	iotbroker	src.main.java.com...mqttsn.MqttsnClient.java	processSuback
72	iotbroker	src.main.java.com...mqttsn.TimersMap.java	store
73	iotbroker	src.main.java.com...ui.LoginPane.java	loginBtnClicked
74	jedis	src.main.java...jedis.JedisClusterCommand.java	runWithRetries
75	jedis	src.main.java...jedis.JedisPubSub.java	process
76	jedis	src.main.java...jedis.JedisSentinelPool.java	run
77	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...DMOPSO.java	fitnessFunction
78	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...ScalarizationUtils.java	tradeoffUtility
79	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...GWASFGARanking.java	computeRanking
80	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...GWASFGARanking.java	rankUnfeasibleSolutions

81	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...MOCHC45.java	run
82	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...AbstractMOEAD.java	fitnessFunction
83	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...ConstraintMOEAD.java	updateNeighborhood
84	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...MOEADD.java	deleteCrowdRegion1
85	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...MOEADD.java	deleteCrowdRegion2
86	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...MOEADD.java	deleteRankOne
87	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...MOEADD.java	matingSelection
88	jmetal	src.main.java...MOEADD.java_nondominated_sorting	delete
89	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...EnvironmentalSelection.java	execute
90	jmetal	src.main.java.org.uma.jmetal...LZ09.java	objective

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91	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng.spagobi...AbstractDriverRuntime.java	loadAdmissibleValues
92	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng.spagobi...DriversValidationAPI.java	getValidationErrorOnCheck
93	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng.spagobi...ExecutionInstance.java	applyViewpoint
94	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng.spagobi...ExecutionInstance.java	getValidationErrorOnCheck
95	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng.spagobi...SelfServiceDataSetCRUD.java	validateDataset
96	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng...MenuListJSONSerializerForREST.java	createUserMenuElement
97	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng...DocumentCompositionUtils.java	getExecutionUrl
98	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng.spagobi...KpiService.java	checkConflictsWithKpi
99	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng...GeoLayerJSONDeserializer.java	deserialize
100	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng.spagobi...SchedulerServiceSupplier.java	getChronExpression
101	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng...AbstractAssociativityManager.java	getSelections

102	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng...DatasetManagementAPI.java	setDataSetParameters(IDataSet-Map-String,String-String)
103	knowage-core	src.main.java...GeoSpatialDimensionDatasetValidator.java	doValidateDataset
104	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng.spagobi...MenuUtilities.java	getMenuItems(SourceBean-SourceBean-IEngUserProfile)
105	knowage-core	src.main.java.it.eng.spagobi...MenuUtilities.java	getMenuPath
106	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework.algorithm.CMAES.java	checkEigenSystem
107	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework.algorithm.CMAES.java	eigendecomposition
108	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework.algorithm.CMAES.java	samplePopulation
109	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework.algorithm.CMAES.java	tql2
110	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework.algorithm.CMAES.java	updateDistribution
111	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework.algorithm.DBEA.java	updateIdealPointAndIntercepts
112	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework.algorithm.DBEA.java	updatePopulation
113	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework...jmetal.JMetalAlgorithms.java	getAlgorithm
114	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework.algorithm.MOEADE.java	updateSolution
115	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework...MSOPSRankedPopulation.java	update
116	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework.algorithm.NSGAII.java	iterate
117	MOEAFramework	src...ReferencePointNondominatedSortingPopulation.java	calculateIntercepts
118	MOEAFramework	src...ReferencePointNondominatedSortingPopulation.java	lsolve
119	MOEAFramework	src...ReferencePointNondominatedSortingPopulation.java	truncate
120	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework...SPEA2.java	evaluate
121	MOEAFramework	src.org.moeaframework...StandardAlgorithms.java	getAlgorithm

Table B.2: Results obtained for methods under study in open-source projects for two objectives (*Extractions (E)*, *CC (C)*). Each column represents, respectively, the index of each method (see Table B.1), number of solutions obtained for the method, reference point used for the method to compute the HV, normalized HV (N-HV), and the median and inter-quartile range (*IQR*) for the two objective functions.

ID	No. sol	Reference (<i>E,C</i>)	N-HV	Extractions		CC	
				<i>Median</i>	<i>IQR</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>IQR</i>
1	1	(5,2)	1.00	4.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
2	2	(5,3)	0.67	3.0	1.00	1.5	0.50
3	3	(8,4)	0.53	6.0	2.00	2.0	1.00
4	1	(3,3)	1.00	2.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
5	2	(5,6)	0.62	3.5	0.50	3.5	1.50
6	2	(4,5)	0.60	2.5	0.50	2.0	2.00
7	3	(6,12)	0.57	4.0	1.00	8.0	3.00
8	2	(5,6)	0.62	3.5	0.50	3.5	1.50
9	1	(5,2)	1.00	4.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
10	2	(4,3)	0.67	2.5	0.50	1.0	1.00
11	2	(4,4)	0.67	2.5	0.50	2.0	1.00
12	1	(3,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
13	1	(3,3)	1.00	2.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
14	1	(3,1)	1.00	2.0	0.00	0.0	0.00
15	4	(12,6)	0.59	7.0	3.25	3.5	1.50
16	3	(8,6)	0.73	3.0	2.50	2.0	2.00
17	3	(6,4)	0.67	3.0	1.50	2.0	1.00
18	3	(8,11)	0.53	6.0	2.00	9.0	1.00
19	2	(4,14)	0.60	2.5	0.50	11.0	2.00
20	3	(5,4)	0.67	3.0	1.00	2.0	1.00
21	4	(9,9)	0.60	6.0	2.50	3.5	4.00
22	3	(6,4)	0.58	4.0	1.50	2.0	1.00
23	3	(11,3)	0.67	3.0	4.00	1.0	1.00
24	3	(11,3)	0.67	3.0	4.00	1.0	1.00
25	3	(17,4)	0.59	8.0	6.00	2.0	1.00

26	1	(3,1)	1.00	2.0	0.00	0.0	0.00
27	1	(3,1)	1.00	2.0	0.00	0.0	0.00
28	3	(11,4)	0.58	6.0	3.50	2.0	1.00
29	2	(5,4)	0.56	3.0	1.00	2.0	1.00
30	8	(15,15)	0.59	9.5	3.75	7.0	7.00
31	1	(4,11)	1.00	3.0	0.00	10.0	0.00
32	1	(3,1)	1.00	2.0	0.00	0.0	0.00
33	1	(3,4)	1.00	2.0	0.00	3.0	0.00
34	2	(4,8)	0.58	2.5	0.50	4.5	2.50
35	2	(7,3)	0.60	4.0	2.00	1.5	0.50
36	3	(10 3)	0.62	4.0	3.50	1.0	1.00
37	2	(8,2)	0.58	4.5	2.50	0.5	0.50
38	1	(3,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
39	2	(4,2)	0.75	2.5	0.50	0.5	0.50
40	1	(4,2)	1.00	3.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
41	4	(9,11)	0.63	5.5	1.75	6.5	2.25
42	2	(10,13)	0.56	8.0	1.00	11.0	1.00
43	1	(4,2)	1.00	3.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
44	1	(7,7)	1.00	6.0	0.00	6.0	0.00
45	2	(7,4)	0.50	4.5	1.50	2.0	1.00
46	1	(5,4)	1.00	4.0	0.00	3.0	0.00
47	3	(10,14)	0.67	8.0	1.00	11.0	1.50
48	2	(5,5)	0.75	3.5	0.50	3.5	0.50
49	1	(5,4)	1.00	4.0	0.00	3.0	0.00
50	4	(7,7)	0.55	4.5	1.50	4.5	1.75
51	3	(9,7)	0.70	5.0	2.00	4.0	1.50
52	1	(4,2)	1.00	3.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
53	1	(6,15)	1.00	5.0	0.00	14.0	0.00
54	2	(5,5)	0.62	3.5	0.50	2.5	1.50
55	4	(18,12)	0.63	12.5	6.00	7.5	2.00
56	2	(10,5)	0.58	6.5	2.50	3.5	0.50
57	2	(10,4)	0.44	6.5	2.50	2.0	1.00

58	2	(8,5)	0.67	6.0	1.00	3.5	0.50
59	1	(6,7)	1.00	5.0	0.00	6.0	0.00
60	1	(4,3)	1.00	3.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
61	1	(3,14)	1.00	2.0	0.00	13.0	0.00
62	2	(6,3)	0.62	3.5	1.50	1.5	0.50
63	2	(6,3)	0.62	3.5	1.50	1.5	0.50
64	2	(6,3)	0.67	4.0	1.00	1.5	0.50
65	1	(3,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
66	3	(6,4)	0.67	3.0	1.50	2.0	1.00
67	2	(6,5)	0.67	4.5	0.50	3.0	1.00
68	2	(4,6)	0.60	2.5	0.50	3.0	2.00
69	1	(3,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
70	1	(3,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
71	2	(4,3)	0.75	2.5	0.50	1.5	0.50
72	1	(3,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
73	2	(4,5)	0.67	2.5	0.50	3.0	1.00
74	4	(7,12)	0.56	4.5	1.50	7.5	4.00
75	2	(15,3)	0.54	8.5	5.50	1.5	0.50
76	2	(5,6)	0.67	3.0	1.00	4.5	0.50
77	1	(3,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
78	1	(3,3)	1.00	2.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
79	1	(4,2)	1.00	3.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
80	1	(3,3)	1.00	2.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
81	2	(11,2)	0.56	6.0	4.00	0.5	0.50
82	2	(6,5)	0.62	3.5	1.50	3.5	0.50
83	1	(3,3)	1.00	2.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
84	2	(4,2)	0.75	2.5	0.50	0.5	0.50
85	2	(6,4)	0.67	4.0	1.00	2.5	0.50
86	2	(7,4)	0.62	4.5	1.50	2.5	0.50
87	3	(7,7)	0.50	5.0	1.00	5.0	2.50
88	2	(10,3)	0.58	6.5	2.50	1.5	0.50
89	1	(5,3)	1.00	4.0	0.00	2.0	0.00

90	1	(4,2)	1.00	3.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
91	1	(6,6)	1.00	5.0	0.00	5.0	0.00
92	2	(8,4)	0.62	5.5	1.50	2.5	0.50
93	2	(5,12)	0.58	3.5	0.50	8.5	2.50
94	2	(8,4)	0.62	5.5	1.50	2.5	0.50
95	3	(8,9)	0.58	6.0	1.00	4.0	3.50
96	1	(7,15)	1.00	6.0	0.00	14.0	0.00
98	3	(14,4)	0.63	7.0	4.00	2.0	1.00
99	2	(11,3)	0.57	7.0	3.00	1.5	0.50
100	3	(15,7)	0.41	12.0	5.00	4.0	1.50
101	4	(17,10)	0.82	5.5	3.75	3.0	3.50
102	2	(6,6)	0.62	4.5	0.50	3.5	1.50
103	3	(14,5)	0.68	6.0	4.50	2.0	1.50
104	2	(4,11)	0.62	2.5	0.50	8.5	1.50
105	3	(6,4)	0.67	3.0	1.50	2.0	1.00
106	1	(3,3)	1.00	2.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
107	2	(4,4)	0.67	2.5	0.50	2.0	1.00
108	1	(4,3)	1.00	3.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
109	2	(7,3)	0.62	4.5	1.50	1.5	0.50
110	2	(5,4)	0.75	3.5	0.50	2.5	0.50
111	2	(7,3)	0.62	4.5	1.50	1.5	0.50
112	2	(4,3)	0.67	2.5	0.50	1.0	1.00
113	2	(5,3)	0.75	3.5	0.50	1.5	0.50
114	2	(4,5)	0.62	2.5	0.50	2.5	1.50
115	1	(3,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
116	3	(7,4)	0.67	3.0	2.00	2.0	1.00
117	2	(4,6)	0.60	2.5	0.50	3.0	2.00
118	3	(5,4)	0.67	3.0	1.00	1.0	1.50
119	2	(12,3)	0.55	6.5	4.50	1.5	0.50
120	1	(3,1)	1.00	2.0	0.00	0.0	0.00
121	1	(4,2)	1.00	3.0	0.00	1.0	0.00

Table B.3: Results obtained for methods under study in open-source projects. Each column represents, respectively, the index of each method (see Table B.1), number of solutions obtained for the method, the reference point used for the method (*Extractions (E)*, *CC (C)*, *LOC (L)*) to compute the HV, normalized HV (N-HV), and the median and inter-quartile range (*IQR*) for the three objective functions.

ID	No. sol	Reference	N-	Extractions		CC		LOC	
		(<i>E,C,L</i>)	HV	Median	IQR	Median	IQR	Median	IQR
1	19	(20,11,11)	0.86	9.0	7.50	3.0	1.50	5.0	3.00
2	2	(5,3,3)	0.58	3.0	1.00	1.5	0.50	1.5	0.50
3	13	(12,10,15)	0.79	7.0	4.00	3.0	2.00	4.0	3.00
4	5	(8,8,24)	0.83	4.0	4.00	2.0	1.00	13.0	11.00
5	13	(12,10,26)	0.73	5.0	3.00	5.0	2.00	11.0	5.00
6	6	(5,8,23)	0.49	3.0	1.50	3.5	1.75	6.5	10.75
7	10	(8,14,26)	0.59	5.0	1.75	8.0	3.50	10.5	9.00
8	11	(11,8,31)	0.66	5.0	4.00	4.0	3.00	9.0	6.00
9	12	(16,8,20)	0.55	9.0	6.25	3.5	2.25	11.0	6.75
10	8	(8,10,11)	0.61	3.5	2.50	2.0	2.00	3.5	4.50
11	15	(10,8,20)	0.66	5.0	3.00	3.0	2.00	8.0	5.00
12	1	(3,2,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
13	1	(3,3,3)	1.00	2.0	0.00	2.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
14	1	(3,1,1)	1.00	2.0	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.0	0.00
15	9	(13,8,42)	0.50	8.0	2.00	4.0	2.00	36.0	4.00
16	8	(9,9,16)	0.54	4.0	3.50	3.5	3.00	6.5	6.00
17	6	(7,6,15)	0.67	3.0	2.25	2.5	1.00	4.0	4.00
18	5	(9,11,33)	0.35	7.0	1.00	9.0	1.00	30.0	2.00
19	2	(4,14,14)	0.40	2.5	0.50	11.0	2.00	12.5	0.50
20	20	(13,12,32)	0.68	6.5	6.25	5.0	3.25	10.0	6.75
21	12	(9,9,16)	0.40	7.0	1.25	5.0	3.25	7.0	7.25
22	7	(7,12,9)	0.72	3.0	2.00	3.0	1.50	6.0	5.00
23	11	(18,9,24)	0.85	9.0	7.50	1.0	1.50	4.0	8.00
24	11	(18,5,24)	0.74	9.0	7.50	1.0	1.50	4.0	7.00
25	19	(18,12,29)	0.58	8.0	4.50	4.0	4.00	17.0	7.50

26	1	(3,1,1)	1.00	2.0	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.0	0.00
27	1	(3,1,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	0.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
28	12	(12,11,19)	0.51	6.0	3.25	4.0	3.50	12.0	3.50
29	6	(11,5,9)	0.75	4.5	4.75	1.5	1.75	2.5	2.50
30	10	(15,15,47)	0.44	10.5	4.50	5.0	5.50	37.0	7.50
31	2	(5,11,14)	0.57	3.5	0.50	10.0	0.00	10.0	3.00
32	1	(3,1,2)	1.00	2.0	0.00	0.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
33	1	(3,4,3)	1.00	2.0	0.00	3.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
34	2	(4,8,15)	0.51	2.0	0.50	4.5	2.50	8.0	6.00
35	5	(9,4,7)	0.62	4.0	3.00	2.0	1.00	3.0	2.00
36	12	(10,6,18)	0.69	4.5	3.50	2.0	1.25	4.5	6.50
37	2	(8,2,7)	0.51	4.5	2.50	0.5	0.50	3.0	3.00
38	1	(3,2,3)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00	2.0	0.00
39	2	(4,2,6)	0.54	2.5	0.50	0.5	0.50	2.5	2.50
40	20	(15,12,27)	0.73	6.5	6.00	4.0	3.25	7.5	3.75
41	11	(14,11,19)	0.68	8.0	4.00	6.0	2.00	9.0	7.00
42	4	(10,14,48)	0.49	7.5	1.25	12.5	1.50	34.0	6.75
43	9	(15,8,10)	0.55	6.0	6.00	3.0	2.00	6.0	3.00
44	2	(8,7,20)	0.75	6.5	0.50	6.0	0.00	18.5	0.50
45	16	(15,10,20)	0.64	7.0	5.25	3.5	3.00	7.5	6.00
46	4	(9,10,14)	0.42	6.0	2.50	4.0	3.00	10.0	2.75
47	3	(10,14,26)	0.67	8.0	1.00	11.0	1.50	25.0	0.00
48	2	(5,5,10)	0.53	3.5	0.50	3.5	0.50	5.5	3.50
49	7	(10,11,12)	0.35	6.0	2.50	8.0	3.50	9.0	1.50
50	5	(7,7,13)	0.32	5.0	2.00	4.0	2.00	9.0	1.00
51	5	(10,7,10)	0.52	8.0	3.00	4.0	2.00	6.0	2.00
52	17	(9,11,40)	0.49	5.0	2.00	5.0	4.00	20.0	15.00
53	1	(6,15,43)	1.00	5.0	0.00	14.0	0.00	42.0	0.00
54	5	(5,8,17)	0.61	3.0	1.00	4.0	3.00	7.0	3.00
55	9	(18,13,31)	0.64	10.0	2.00	9.0	3.00	21.0	5.00
56	14	(13,12,14)	0.59	9.0	3.50	4.5	2.00	8.0	3.75
57	17	(23,7,15)	0.70	10.0	4.00	2.0	3.00	6.0	4.00

58	4	(8,6,20)	0.45	6.0	0.50	4.0	0.50	9.5	6.25
59	2	(6,8,11)	0.67	5.0	0.00	6.5	0.50	9.0	1.00
60	2	(7,6,8)	0.53	4.5	1.50	3.5	1.50	6.5	0.50
61	2	(4,15,33)	0.62	2.5	0.50	13.5	0.50	31.5	0.50
62	2	(6,3,3)	0.56	3.5	1.50	1.5	0.50	1.5	0.50
63	2	(6,3,4)	0.53	3.5	1.50	1.5	0.50	1.5	1.50
64	5	(7,7,11)	0.55	4.0	2.00	3.0	2.00	4.0	1.00
65	1	(3,2,15)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00	14.0	0.00
66	4	(6,6,15)	0.69	2.5	1.50	2.5	1.75	3.5	4.00
67	5	(10,7,18)	0.46	5.0	5.00	4.0	1.00	12.0	4.00
68	4	(5,6,7)	0.38	3.5	1.25	2.5	1.75	2.5	2.25
69	1	(3,2,15)	1.00	2.0	0.00	1.0	0.00	14.0	0.00
70	5	(7,5,10)	0.48	4.0	2.00	2.0	1.00	6.0	3.00
71	6	(7,7,17)	0.56	3.5	1.75	2.5	1.75	9.0	4.75
72	5	(7,5,9)	0.51	4.0	2.00	2.0	1.00	5.0	3.00
73	3	(4,9,16)	0.55	2.0	0.50	4.0	3.00	10.0	3.00
74	9	(8,14,41)	0.57	5.0	2.00	9.0	5.00	27.0	7.00
75	12	(16,8,8)	0.65	9.0	4.25	2.5	1.25	3.0	1.50
76	2	(5,6,12)	0.52	3.0	1.00	4.5	0.50	6.5	4.50
77	8	(9,8,12)	0.66	4.5	3.50	2.0	2.25	4.5	2.25
78	1	(3,3,1)	1.00	2.0	0.00	2.0	0.00	0.0	0.00
79	5	(17,9,4)	0.55	8.0	5.00	5.0	3.00	2.0	1.00
80	1	(3,3,16)	1.00	2.0	0.00	2.0	0.00	15.0	0.00
81	5	(11,4,6)	0.61	3.0	2.00	1.0	0.00	2.0	1.00
82	5	(7,14,19)	0.76	3.0	3.00	4.0	1.00	10.0	9.00
83	4	(6,9,7)	0.50	2.5	1.50	4.5	5.25	3.5	1.75
84	2	(4,2,22)	0.51	2.5	0.50	0.5	0.50	11.0	10.00
85	17	(9,11,42)	0.66	6.0	2.00	4.0	3.00	11.0	8.00
86	13	(14,9,27)	0.74	6.0	3.00	3.0	1.00	8.0	8.00
87	20	(15,11,16)	0.61	8.0	5.00	5.0	3.00	5.5	6.50
88	20	(16,8,18)	0.70	7.0	4.50	3.0	2.50	6.0	5.50
89	15	(17,9,12)	0.69	9.0	6.50	3.0	2.50	5.0	3.00

90	1	(4,2,2)	1.00	3.0	0.00	1.0	0.00	1.0	0.00
91	5	(8,15,35)	0.32	6.0	1.00	7.0	2.00	29.0	5.00
92	5	(12,9,6)	0.54	8.0	2.00	4.0	2.00	3.0	1.00
93	2	(5,12,15)	0.54	3.5	0.50	8.5	2.50	13.5	0.50
94	6	(12,9,7)	0.60	8.5	1.75	4.5	3.25	3.0	0.75
95	12	(15,11,49)	0.70	7.0	2.25	4.5	5.25	34.0	12.25
96	3	(9,15,41)	0.67	7.0	1.00	14.0	0.00	25.0	8.00
97	7	(9,14,70)	0.39	7.0	1.00	10.0	4.50	43.0	32.00
98	11	(17,9,5)	0.64	10.0	6.00	3.0	3.00	2.0	1.50
99	7	(15,7,11)	0.74	5.0	4.00	2.0	1.00	7.0	2.50
100	9	(16,11,40)	0.52	6.0	8.00	6.0	3.00	24.0	6.00
101	11	(17,10,10)	0.69	7.0	5.00	3.0	3.00	4.0	3.50
102	8	(12,9,7)	0.69	5.0	2.50	5.0	2.25	4.0	2.25
103	17	(15,12,22)	0.80	6.0	4.00	4.0	4.00	8.0	3.00
104	6	(6,13,34)	0.54	3.5	1.00	9.0	3.50	13.0	17.00
105	4	(7,4,8)	0.50	4.0	2.50	2.0	0.50	3.5	3.75
106	7	(6,15,18)	0.34	3.0	1.00	8.0	8.00	9.0	6.50
107	3	(4,6,13)	0.61	2.0	0.50	3.0	2.00	2.0	5.50
108	9	(10,12,19)	0.73	4.0	2.00	4.0	3.00	6.0	3.00
109	18	(11,11,32)	0.72	4.0	2.75	3.5	4.75	11.5	12.75
110	20	(23,6,36)	0.78	9.5	8.25	3.0	2.00	9.5	8.50
111	10	(18,6,9)	0.67	6.5	7.25	2.0	0.75	3.5	3.50
112	7	(11,7,18)	0.66	5.0	4.00	5.0	3.00	3.0	1.00
113	12	(20 8,12)	0.70	5.5	7.00	2.5	3.50	3.5	2.25
114	3	(4,5,6)	0.42	3.0	0.50	2.0	1.50	3.0	2.00
115	3	(4,5,8)	0.52	2.0	0.50	3.0	1.50	1.0	3.50
116	5	(9,4,17)	0.55	5.0	3.00	2.0	0.00	7.0	6.00
117	8	(10,8,14)	0.73	4.0	3.50	3.0	3.25	5.0	5.50
118	11	(22,4,8)	0.67	8.0	7.00	1.0	0.50	4.0	4.00
119	18	(15,12,16)	0.67	8.5	6.75	3.5	2.00	6.0	5.00
120	8	(18,8,5)	0.60	5.5	6.00	2.0	2.50	2.0	2.00
121	5	(11,3,9)	0.74	5.0	3.00	1.0	0.00	5.0	3.00

```

1 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception {
2     usedHosts.add(this);
3     if (ttl == 0) { //Problem in routing
4         throw new Exception("Routing problem, TTL is null : packet to "
5             + ip + " deleted on host " + this.getName());
6     }
7     if (!hasIP(ip)) { //Packet not arrived
8         Host nextHost = null;
9         List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
10        for (Host directlyAccessibleHost : directlyAccessibleHosts) {
11            if (directlyAccessibleHost.hasIP(ip) // If the packet is for a neighbour,
12                // we send it to him
13
14                nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
15        }
16        if (nextHost != null) {
17            nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
18        } else { //We have to look in the routing table
19            List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
20            IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
21            boolean nextHostFound = false;
22            for (Host aDirectlyAccessible : directlyAccessible) {
23                if (aDirectlyAccessible.hasIP(nextIP)) { //Search the nextHop host object
24                    aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
25                    nextHostFound = true;
26                }
27            }
28            if (!nextHostFound) { //Routing problem
29                throw new Exception("Routing problem, there is no route corresponding
30                    to the packet or the destination host is on the internet");
31            }
32        }
33    }

```

(a) Original method.

```

1 public void routeAPacketTo(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts) throws Exception
2 {
3     usedHosts.add(this);
4     if (ttl == 0) { //Problem in routing
5         throw new Exception("Routing problem, TTL is null : packet to "
6             + ip + " deleted on host " + this.getName());
7     }
8     if (!hasIP(ip)) { //Packet not arrived
9         Host nextHost = null;
10        List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
11        forwardToDirectHostOrRoutingTable(ip, ttl, usedHosts, nextHost,
12            directlyAccessibleHosts);
13    }
14 }
15 private void forwardToDirectHostOrRoutingTable(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host>
16     usedHosts, List<Host> directlyAccessibleHosts) {
17     for (Host directlyAccessibleHost : directlyAccessibleHosts) {
18         if (directlyAccessibleHost.hasIP(ip) // If the packet is for a neighbour,
19             // we send it to him
20
21             nextHost = directlyAccessibleHost;
22     }
23     if (nextHost != null) {
24         nextHost.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
25     } else { //We have to look in the routing table
26         List<Host> directlyAccessible = getDirectlyAccessibleHosts();
27         forwardViaRoutingTable(ip, ttl, usedHosts, directlyAccessible);
28     }
29 }
30 private void forwardViaRoutingTable(IPAddress ip, int ttl, List<Host> usedHosts, List<
31     Host> directlyAccessible) throws Exception {
32     IPAddress nextIP = this.getRoutingTable().getNextHop(ip);
33     boolean nextHostFound = false;
34     for (Host aDirectlyAccessible : directlyAccessible) {
35         if (aDirectlyAccessible.hasIP(nextIP)) { //Search the nextHop host object
36             aDirectlyAccessible.routeAPacketTo(ip, ttl - 1, usedHosts);
37             nextHostFound = true;
38         }
39     }
40     if (!nextHostFound) { //Routing problem
41         throw new Exception("Routing problem, there is no route corresponding

```

(b) Refactored version.

Figure B.1: Extract method refactoring applied to solution s2 in method routeAPacketTo of the running example in Figure 2.7, using the hybrid method algorithm to solve the multi-objective ILP problem.

Figure B.2: Extract method refactoring applied to solution s2 in method `routeAPacketTo` of the running example.

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